

16th International Conference "Laser Optics 2014"

St. Petersburg, Russia, June 30 - July 04, 2014

		Holiday Inn Moskovskye Vorota										
		Floor 1	Floor 2				Floor 3					
		Hall Ginsburg	Hall Petrov- Vodkin 1	Hall Petrov- Vodkin 2	Hall Petrov- Vodkin 3	Hall Levinson	Hall Deyneka 1+2	Hall Stenberg 1	Hall Stenberg 2	Hall Richter 1+2	Hall Pudovkin 1+2	
30.06 Monday	09:00-10:30	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Registration
	10:30-11:00	Opening the conference	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	11:00-14:00	Plenary	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	14:00-15:00		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	15:00-18:00		SM2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	18:00-19:00		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	19:00-20:00	Welcome party										
01.07 Tuesday	09:00-11:00		R8	SY1			R6	YS	SM2	SM1	R3	R1: Solid-State Lasers for System Applications R2: High Power Laser Systems and Facilities R3: Semiconductor Lasers, Materials and Applications R4: Laser Beam Control R5: Super-Intense Light Fields and Ultra-
	11:30-13:30		R8	SY1			R6	YS	SM2	SM1	R3	
	15:00-17:00	Poster session: YS + R8	R1	SY1			R6	R4	SM2	SM1	R3	
	17:30-19:30	Exhibition	R1	SY1			R6	R4	SM2	SM1	R3	
02.07 Wednesday	09:00-11:30	Poster session: R1	R8	SY1			R6	A1		YS	R5	
	11:30-13:30	Exhibition	R8	SY1			R6	A1		YS	R5	

	15:00-17:00	Poster session: R4 + R6 + SM1 + SM2 Exhibition	R8	SY1		R2	A1	R7	R5	Fast Processes R6: Nanophotonics and Biophotonics R7: Lasers in Environmental Monitoring R8: Nonlinear Photonics: Fundamentals and Applications MS: Memorial session: Professor A.P. Sukhorukov and nonlinear optics R9: Microwave photonics (MWP) SY1: 7th International Symposium on High-Power Fiber Lasers and Their Applications	
	17:30-19:30		R8	SY1	PD	R2	A1	R7	R5		
03.07 Thursday	09:00-11:00	Poster session: R2 + R5 + R7 Exhibition	SY2	SY1		R6	R4	R1	R9	R3	SY2: 3rd International Symposium on Lasers in Medicine SY2-C: Course on Biomedical Optics in Clinical Applications YS: 7th International Conference on Laser Optics for Young Scientists and Engineers PD: Post-deadline SM1: Seminar on Optoelectronics SM2: Seminar on Terahertz Photonics A1: Applying of Progressive Laser Technologies and Equipment in Industry
	11:30-13:30		SY2	SY1	R8	R6	R4	R1	R9	R3	
	15:00-17:00	Poster session: R3 + R9 + SY2 Exhibition	SY2	SY1	MS	R2	R4	R1	R7	R5	
	17:30-19:30		SY2			R2	R4	R1	R7	R5	
04.07 Friday	09:00-11:00		SY2	SY2-C							
	11:30-13:30		SY2	SY2-C							
	15:00-17:00										
	17:30-19:30										

Session: Plenary

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Monday, June 30

11:00-11:45 Code: MoPl-01, Invited

Kivshar Yuri

Shaping light with metamaterials. From nonlinear response to all-dielectric nanophotonics

Yu. Kivshar, Nonlinear Physics Center, Australian National Univ., Australia; National Research University ITMO, Russia

11:45-12:30 Code: MoPl-02, Invited

Krausz Ferenc

Real-Time Observation and Control of Electron Motion

Ferenc Krausz; Max-Planck-Institut für Quantenoptik; Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, Germany

12:30-13:15 Code: MoPl-03, Invited

Krokhin Oleg

Interference of single photons (What is a photon?)

O.N. Krokhin; Lebedev Physical Institute RAS, Russia

13:15-14:00 Code: MoPl-04, Invited

Zheltikov Aleksey

The serendipity of ultrashort guided lightwaves: from quantum physics to life sciences

A.M. Zheltikov; Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia

Session: R1. Solid-State Lasers for System Applications

[top][schedule]

Tuesday, July 1

14:30-15:00 Code: TuR1-01, Invited

Kornev Aleksei

KW-level Q-switched Nd:YAG MOPA lasers

A.F. Kornev, Vavilov State Optical Institute, Russia

15:00-15:15 Code: TuR1-02

Kasyanov Ivan

Periodical double frequency YAG:Nd laser for pumping parametric amplifier

Yu. D. Arapov 1, A.V. Berezin 1, A. V. Bochkov 1, S. G. Grechin 2, A. V. Isaev 1, A. F. Ivanov 1, I. V. Kasyanov 1, A. V. Kolegov 1, A. V. Lukin 1; 1 Russian Federal Nuclear Center - Zababakhin All-Russia Research Institute of Technical Physics, 2 Bauman Moscow State Technical University

15:15-15:30 Code: TuR1-03

Kuznetsov Ivan

High-power thin-disk laser with composite Yb:YAG/YAG active element

Ivan Kuznetsov, Ivan Mukhin, Oleg Palashov; Institute of Applied Physics RAS; Russia

15:30-15:45 Code: TuR1-04

Kuznetsov Ivan

Thin-rod amplifier for fiber lasers scaling

Ivan Kuznetsov, Ivan Mukhin, Oleg Palashov; Institute of Applied Physics RAS, Russia

15:45-16:15 Code: TuR1-05, Invited

Liu Xingsheng

Study of the Key Aspects in Developing kW-Level Diode Lasers for Solid State Laser Pumping

Xiaoning Li, Jingwei Wang, Wanshao Cai, Bei Hao, Dong Hou, Hui Liu, Pu Zhang, Xingsheng Liu; Xi'an Institute of Optics and Precision Mechanics of China Academy of Sciences; Focuslight Technologies Co.,Ltd., China; P.R. China

16:15-16:30 Code: TuR1-06

Kozlov A.B.

Development of High-Power Disk Laser

A.B. Kozlov, N.P. Badalyan, A.V. Shestakov, I.A. Shestakova; RDI "Polyus"; Russia; RDI "Polyus"

16:30-16:45 Code: TuR1-07

Lebedev Vyacheslav

High-Energy, Passively Q-Switched, Diode-Pumped Nd:YAG Laser with Reciprocal Multiloop, Self-pumped Phase-Conjugate Cavity

V.F. Lebedev^{1,2}, A.P. Pogoda^{1,2}, A.S. Boreyshol^{1,2}, V.A. Konjushkin³, S.N. Smetanin⁴, A.V. Fedin⁴; 1 Baltic State Technical University, 2 Laser Systems Ltd, 3 General Physics Institute RAS, 4 Kovrov State Technological Academy; Russia

16:45-17:00 Code: TuR1-08

Wang Dan

Influence of input laser spectrum widths on extracting powers in Nd:YAG laser amplifiers

Dan Wang, Lixin Tong, Tangjian Zhou, Juntao Wang, Hao Hu, Qingsong Gao, Chun Tang; Institute of Applied Electronics CAEP, China; P.R. China

Tuesday, July 1

17:30-18:00 Code: TuR1-09, Invited

Mironov Sergey

Laser system for generation 3D ellipsoidal UV pulses

Sergey Mironov¹, Ekaterina Gacheval, Anatoly Poteomkin¹, Victor Zelenogorskiy¹, Alexey Andrianov¹, Efim Khazanov¹, Mikhail Krasilnikov², Frank Stephan², Evgeny Syresin³; ¹ IAP RAS, Russia; ² DESY, Germany; ³ JINR, Russia

18:00-18:15 Code: TuR1-10

Nyushkov Boris

Universal femtosecond fiber-optic clockwork

B.N. Nyushkov, V.S. Pivtsov, N.A. Koliada, I.I. Korel, V.I. Denisov, and S.N. Bagayev; Institute of laser physics SB RAS; Russia

18:15-18:30 Code: TuR1-11

Sazonkin Stanislav G.

Sub-100 fs similariton generation in the hybrid mode-locked erbium-doped fiber ring laser

Stanislav G. Sazonkin ¹, Alexander A. Krylov ², Stanislav O. Leonov ¹, Dmitriy A. Dvoretzkiy ¹, Vyacheslav V. Grebenyukov ³, Anatoly S.

Pozharov ³, Elena D. Obratsova ³; ¹ Bauman Moscow State Technical University; ² Fiber Optics Research Center of the RAS; ³ General Physics Institute of the RAS; Russia

18:30-18:45 Code: TuR1-12

Michailovas Kirilas

High average power high repetition rate chirped pulse amplifier for OPCPA pumping

Kirilas Michailovas ¹, Andrejus Michailovas ¹, Audrius Zaukevicus ¹, Valerijus Smilgevicius ²; ¹ EKSPALA and Center for Physical Science and Technology, ² Laser Research Center, Vilnius Univ.; Lithuania

18:45-19:00 Code: TuR1-13

Chernysheva Maria

High Energy Hybrid Mode-Locked Thulium-doped Fiber Laser

M.A. Chernysheva ¹, A.A. Krylov ¹, E.M. Dianov ¹, C. Mou ², R.N. Arif ², A. Rozhin ², S.K. Turitsyn ², M.H. Ruemmeli ³; ¹ Fiber Optics Research Center RAS, Russia; ² Aston Institute of Photonics Technology, Aston University, UK; ³ IFW Dresden, Germany

19:00-19:15 Code: TuR1-14

Polyakov Vadim

A RF standard based on a longitudinal modes beat note of a frequency locked laser

Vadim M. Polyakov ¹, Evgeniy A. Viktorov ¹, Anton V. Kovalev ¹, Oleg Orlov ²; ¹ National Research University ITMO, ² Mendeleyev Institute for Metrology, Russia

19:15-19:30 Code: TuR1-15

Mareev Evgeniy

Cavitation and shock waves in water, stimulated by laser filament

F.V. Potemkin, E.I. Mareev; Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia

Thursday, July 3

09:00-09:30 Code: ThR1-16, Invited

Arie Ady

Adiabatic Frequency Conversion

Ady Arie; Tel-Aviv University, Israel

09:30-09:45 Code: ThR1-17

Gao Chungqing

Dual-wavelength laser emitting at 1617 nm and 1645 nm in a resonantly pumped Er:YAG laser

Ran Wang, Qing Ye, Mingwei Gao, Wenyan Li, Li Liu, Chungqing Gao; Beijing Institute of Technology; P.R. China

09:45-10:00 Code: ThR1-18

Gorbachenya Konstantin

Laser Properties of In-band Pumped Er:YVO₄ and Er:KY(WO₄)₂ Crystals

K.N. Gorbachenya ¹, V.E. Kisel ¹, A.S. Yasukevich ¹, N.V. Kuleshov ¹, A.A. Pavlyuk ², V.N. Matrosov ³; ¹ Center for Optical Materials and Technologies; ² A.V. Nikolaev Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, ³ Solix Ltd; Belarus

10:00-10:15 Code: ThR1-19

Ivanov Vladimir

Pulse Periodic 1.54 μm Raman Laser Based on Atermal KGW:Nd³⁺ Active Element

V.N. Ivanov², A.V. Sandulenko², E.K. Serdyuk¹, O.B. Storoshuk³, A.N. Titov¹, I.V. Mochalov¹; ¹ St.Petersburg National Research University ITMO, ² Research and Technology Institute of Optical Material Science, ³ Research and Production Company "Karat", Russia

10:15-10:30 Code: ThR1-20

Nejezchleb Karel

BaW04 Intracavity Pumped Eye-safe Raman Laser

Karel Nejezchleb ¹, Nickalai Kapitch ¹, Václav Škoda ¹, Helena Jelínková ², Lucia Koubíková ², Jan Šulc ², Pavel Boháček ³, Zdeněk Remeš ³; ¹ Crytur Ltd., ² FNCS CTU Prague, ³ Inst. of Phys.; Czech Republic

10:30-10:45 Code: ThR1-21

Tarabrin Mikhail

Testing of Cr:ZnSe Laser with Intracavity Methane Cell in 77-300 K Temperature Range

M.K. Tarabrin 1, M.P. Frolov 2,3, M.A. Gubin 2, A.N. Kireev 2, Yu.V. Korostelin 2, V.I. Kozlovsky 2, V.A. Lazarev 1, A.B. Pnirov 1, Yu.P. Podmar'kov 2,3, D.A. Shelestov 1, A.S. Shelkovnikov 2, D.A. Tyurikov 2; 1 Bauman Moscow State Technical University, 2 P.N.Lebedev Physical Institute RAS, 3 Moscow Institute of Physics and Technology, Russia

10:45-11:00 Code: ThR1-22

Antipov Oleg

High-efficiency oscillations at 1940 nm and 2070 nm in diode-pumped Tm:Lu2O3 ceramics lasers and their OPO frequency conversion

O.L. Antipov 1, A.A. Novikov 1, I.D. Eranov 1, D.B. Kolker 2; 1 Institute of Applied Physics RAS, 2 Novosibirsk State Technical University, Russia

Thursday, July 3

11:30-11:45 Code: ThR1-23

Narivonchik Anton

100 mJ/100 Hz Mid-IR laser source

A.G. Kalintsev, U.V. Katsev, A. F. Kornev, A. S. Narivonchik, D.O. Oborotov, A. L. Pavlova, V.P. Pokrovskiy, V. A. Serebryakov, V.K. Stupnikov, S.S. Terekhov; Vavilov State Optical Institute, Russia

11:45-12:15 Code: ThR1-24, Invited

Loiko Pavel

Europium-Doped Double Tungstates: Novel Crystals for Visible Lasers

P.A. Loiko 1, N.V. Kuleshov 1, K.V. Yumashev 1, V.I. Dashkevich 2, V.A. Orlovich 2, S.N. Bagaev 3, S.M. Vatnik 3, A.A. Pavlyuk 4; 1 Belarusian National Technical University, 2 B.I. Stepanov Institute of Physics NAS Belarus, Belarus; 3 Institute of Laser Physics SB RAS, 4 A.V. Nikolaev Institute of Inorganic Chemistry SB RAS, Russia

12:15-12:30 Code: ThR1-25

Grabtchikov Alexander

Up-conversion on the low concentrated rare-earth ions in KGW crystal

I.A. Khodasevich 1, A.S. Grabtchikov 1, A.A. Kornienko 2, E.B. Dunina 2; 1 B.I. Stepanov Institute of Physics NAS Belarus, 2 Vitebsk State Technological University; Belarus

12:30-12:45 Code: ThR1-26

Snetkov Ilya

Specific properties and optical anisotropy parameters measurements of BaF2 and SrF2 materials

I. L. Snetkov, A. I. Yakovlev, O. V. Palashov; Institute of Applied Physics RAS, Russia

12:45-13:00 Code: ThR1-27

Doroshenko MaximSpectroscopic and laser properties of Tm³⁺ ions in fluoride crystals and ceramics.

M.E. Doroshenko 1, V.A. Konyushkin 1, N.A. Nakladov 1, P.P. Fedorov 1, V.V. Osikol, K.A. Martynoval, H. Jelinkova 1, J. Sulc 1; 1 General Physics Institute RAS, Russia; 2 Czech Technical University, Czech Republic

13:00-13:15 Code: ThR1-28

Lyapin Andrey

Laser Properties Of Thulium Doped Calcium Fluoride Crystal

A.A. Lyapin 1, P.A. Ryabochkina 1, A.N. Chabushkin 1. S.N. Ushakov 2, P.P. Fedorov 2; 1 Ogarev Mordovia State University, 2 General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

13:15-13:30 Code: ThR1-29

Krekhova Elena

The special aspects of neodymium and copper-containing phosphate glasses production for large-scaled disk active elements of power high-energy lasers and radiation amplifiers.

L.I. Avakyants 1, V.I. Arbuzov 1.2, M.V. Voroshilova 2, A.V. Dmitryuk 2, A.N. Ignatov 1, S.I. Kramarev 2, E.Yu. Krekhova 1, S.I. Nikitina 2, A.E. Pozdnyakov 1, V.F. Surkova 1, Yu.K. Fyodorov 2; 1 JSC LZOS, 2 RTIOMS named after S. I.Vavilov, Russia

Thursday, July 3

15:00-15:15 Code: ThR1-30

Sudarikov Ivan

Specific aspects of figuring the large-scale disc active elements for lasers and power high energy amplifiers

M. Abdulkadyrov, A. Azerbaev, N. Dobrikov, E. Kurakina, V. Patrikeev, A. Semenov, I. Sudarikov, Y. Sharov; JSC Lytkarino Optical Glass Factory (LZOS), Russia

15:15-15:30 Code: ThR1-31

Nemykin Anton

Analytic solution for multichannel fiber Bragg grating

A.V. Nemykin 1, D.A. Shapiro 1, S. V. Perminov 2; 1 Institute of Automation and Electrometry SB RAS, 2 Rzhanov Institute of Semiconductor Physics SB RAS, Russia

15:30-15:45 Code: ThR1-32

Vyatkin Anton

Three Methods for Calculation of Thermally Induced Beam Distortions in Laser Ceramics

A. G. Vyatkin, E. A. Khazanov; 1 Institute of Applied Physics RAS, Russia

15:45-16:00 Code: ThR1-33

Kapitch Nickalai

Compact stable passively Q-switched flash lamp pumped Nd:YAG laser with Graded Reflectivity Mirror

Nickalai Kapitch, Karel Nejezchleb, Václav Škoda; Crytur Ltd.; Czech Republic

16:00-16:15 Code: ThR1-34

Lebiadok Yahor

Multiwave LD-pumped solid-state lasers for aerosol lidar application

G.I. Ryabtsev, M.V. Bogdanovich, A.V. Grigor'ev, V.V. Kabanov, V.S. Kalinov, O.E. Kostik, Y.V. Lebiadok, K.V. Lepchenkov, F.P. Osipenko, A.G. Ryabtsev, A.P. Chaikovskiy, L.L. Teplyashin, U.S. Tsitavets, M.A. Shchemelev 1; B.I. Stepanov Institute of Physics NASB, 1 Belarusian State University

16:15-16:30 Code: ThR1-35

Ivanov Sergei

Novel, external cavity free, design of Er-Yb laser based on photo-thermo-refractive (PTR) glass

S.A. Ivanov; V.A. Aseev; National Research University ITMO, Russia;

16:30-16:45 Code: ThR1-36

Vitkin Vladimir

Compact Q-switched high repetition rate Nd:YLF laser with 100 mJ pulse energy for airborne lidars

Vladimir V. Vitkin 1, Vadim M. Polyakov 1, Dmitriy I. Lychagin 1, Aleksandr A. Krylov 1, Vyacheslav A. Buchenkov 2, Sergey V. Kashcheev 2; 1 National Research University ITMO, 2 Vavilov State Optical Institute, Russia

16:45-17:00 Code: ThR1-37

Vitkin Vladimir

Ultra compact eye-safe laser for rangefinding

Vadim M. Polyakov 1, Artem A. Kharitonov 1, Vyacheslav A. Buchenkov 2; 1 - NRU ITMO, 2 - Vavilov State Optical Institute, Russia

Poster presentations

Wednesday, July 2

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p01

Fedin Kirill

Stable generation of high-power subnanosecond laser pulses

S. Gagarsky, P. Gnatyuk, M. Inochkin, K. Fedin, L. Khloponin, V. Khramov; National Research University ITMO, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p02

Sadovskiy Sergey

PICOSECOND LASER SYSTEM 193 NM BASED ON SOLID STATE ND:YAG LASER, PARAMETRIC OSCILLATOR AND ARF AMPLIFIER.

S.P. Sadovskiy, P.A. Chizhov, V.V. Bukin, V.M. Brendel, T.V. Dolmatov, Y.N. Polivanov, S.N. Orlov, S.V. Garnov, S.K. Vartapetov; General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p03

Podmar'kov Yuri

High Energy 3450-4150 nm Fe:ZnS Laser

M.P.Frolov, Yu.V.Korostelin, V.I.Kozlovsky, Yu.P.Podmar'kov, S.A.Savinova, Ya.K.Skasyrsky; Lebedev Physical Institute RAS, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p04

Gorajek Lukasz

Ultra low threshold gain-switched Cr:ZnSe laser

Lukasz Gorajek, Jan Jabczynski; Military University of Technology, Poland

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p05

Kalachev Yury

The study of a Tm:YbAG laser pumped at 1678 nm

Yu.D. Zavartsev, A.I. Zagumennyi, Yu.L. Kalachev, S.A. Kutovoi, V.A. Mikhailov, I.A. Scherbakov; General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p06

Fedorov N.A.

Multiwave diode pumped Q-switch ErYLF-laser

N.A.Fedorov, M.V.Inochkin, L.V.Khloponin, V.Yu.Khramov, V.V.Nazarov, D.Yu.Sachkov; National Research University ITMO, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p07

Buchenkov Vyacheslav

1.64 μm Er:YAG laser resonantly pumped by a solid state Er:glass laser

V.A. Buchenkov, D.I. Zhuk, S.I. Klimentev, V.M. Polyakov, A.Yu. Rodionov, National Research University ITMO, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p08

Aseev V.

Temperature dependence of upconversion fluorescence intensity ratio of Er,Yb:YVO₄ and Er,Yb:YGDVO₄ crystals

M. Khodasevich¹, Y. Varaksal, G. Sinitzyn¹, N. Shereshovets¹, V. Aseev²; ¹ B.I.Stepanov Institute of Physics, Belarus; ² National Research University ITMO, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p09

Loiko Pavel

Spectroscopic Characterization of Eu³⁺:KY(WO₄)₂ Laser Crystal

P.A. Loiko¹, N.V. Kuleshov¹, K.V. Yumashev¹, V.I. Dashkevich², V.A. Orlovich², S.N. Bagaev³, S.M. Vatnik³, A.A. Pavlyuk⁴; ¹ Belarusian National Technical University, ² B.I. Stepanov Institute of Physics NAS Belarus, Belarus; ³ Institute of Laser Physics, SB RAS, ⁴ A.V. Nikolaev Institute of Inorganic Chemistry SB RAS, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p10

Pavlova Anna

High Efficiency 50 mJ/1000 Hz Ho:YLF MOPA With Multi-pass Amplifier

A. F. Kornev, A. S. Narivonchik, A. L. Pavlova, V. A. Serebryakov; Lasers and Optical Systems JSC; National Research University ITMO; Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p11

Pruntseva Elena

On the possibility of solid-state 946 nm Nd:YAG laser with high peak and average power development

A. S. Davtian, A. S. Kovyarov, E. A. Pruntseva; Lasers and Optical Systems, JSC, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p12

Ershkov Mikhail

Solid-State Blue Laser by Nonlinear Frequency Conversion of 1.338- μm Nd:YAG Laser Radiation

M.N. Ershkov¹, A.V. Gavrilov¹, S.A. Solokhin¹, S.N. Smetanin², A.O. Schukina¹, A.V. Fedin¹; ¹ Kovrov State Technological Academy, ² General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p13

Ershkov Mikhail

Passive V:YAG Q-Switching Operation of 1.34- μm Nd:YAG Laser with Loop Cavity

M.N. Ershkov¹, A.V. Gavrilov¹, A.V. Fedin¹, S.N. Smetanin¹, S.A. Solokhin¹; ¹ Kovrov State Technological Academy, ² General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p14

Ivanov Pavel

Longitudinally diode pumped Raman solid state lasers based on Gd₃Ga₅O₁₂:Nd³⁺, Y₃Al₅O₁₂:Nd³⁺ and KGd(WO₄)₂:Nd³⁺ active crystals

P.S.Ivanov^{1,2}, I.V.Mochalov², A.V.Sandulenko²; ¹ Research and Technology Institute of Optical Material Science, ² National Research University ITMO, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p15

Ivanov Pavel

1.5 μm miniature and chip longitudinally diode pumped passively Q-switched Raman laser

P.S.Ivanov^{1,2}, I.V.Mochalov², A.V.Sandulenko¹; ¹ Research and Technology Institute of Optical Material Science, ² National Research University ITMO, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p16

Boritko Sergey

Study of the activator impurity distribution by the length of the solid-state laser active element

S.V. Boritko; STC UI RAS, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p17

Khandokhin Pavel

Modeling of Gain Anisotropy Induced by a Linearly Polarized Pump in Nd:YAG Laser

Pavel Khandokhin¹, Nikolai Milovsky²; ¹ Institute of Applied Physics RAS, ² Lobachevsky State University; Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p18

Sergeev Andrey

Two-Photon Recording of Stable Luminescent Centers in Chromone-Doped Polymer Films

A. Ayt¹, V.A.Barachevsky¹, S.V. Gagarskiy², V.V. Kiyko², O.I. Kobeleva¹, M. Krayushkin³, A.N.Sergeev², A.V. Veniaminov², T.M.Valova¹, V.V. Zakharov², Hristo Iglev⁴; ¹ Photochemistry Center RAS; ² National Research University ITMO, ³ Zelinsky Institute of Organic Chemistry,

Russia; 4 Technical University Munich, Germany

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p19

Zakharov Nikita

Efficient and compact pulsed-periodic Cr²⁺:CdSe laser radiating within 2.8 and 3.3 micron wavelength range

N.G. Zakharov 1, Yu.N. Frolov 1, A.V. Muhin 1, C.V. Vorontsov 1, A.V. Larionov 1, V.A. Garyutkin 1, Yu.V. Korostelin 2; 1 RFNC - VNIIEF, 2 LPI RAS, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p20

Mikami Takuya

High-accuracy Sellmeier Equations for GaS_xSe_{1-x} (x=0, 0.09, 0.40, and 1)

Kiyoshi Kato 1 and Takuya Mikami 2 ; 1 Chitose Institute of Science and Technology, 2 Okamoto Optics Works, Inc.; Japan

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p21

Timonin I.V.

INVESTIGATION OF POSSIBILITY OF OSCILLATION AND AMPLIFICATION OF LASER RADIATION IN CERAMIC SAMPLES ND:YAG

E.V. Pozdnyakov, I.V. Timonin; Russian Federal Nuclear Centre 'All-Russian Scientific Research Institute of Experimental Physics'(VNIIEF), Research Institute of Laser Physics, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p22

Zaytseva Olga

Increase of active ions concentration in Cr:Mg₂SiO₄ Laser crystals by the prolonged oxidizing annealing

K.A. Subbotin 1, D.A. Lis 1, E.V. Zharikov 1, A.A. Ivanov 2; 1 General Physics Institute RAS; 2 Photochemistry center RAS, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p23

Zverev Petr

Second harmonic generation in langasite crystal

P.G. Zverev, G.V. Shilova; General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p24

Pushkar Aleksandr

Investigation of the influence of various factors on the efficiency of upconversion processes in BaY₂F₈:Yb³⁺,Pr³⁺,Ce³⁺ with diode-pumped

A. Pushkar 1, T. Uvarova 1, E. Komarnitskaya 2, A.Uvarova 2, A.Ovchinnikov 1; 1 General Physics Institute RAS, 2 National University of Science and Technology "MISIS", Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p25

Mirzaeva Anastasiya

Spectroscopic study of Pr³⁺-doped sodium-yttrium double fluoride crystals (Pr³⁺:NYF)

A. M. Tkachuk, S. E. Ivanova, A. A. Mirzaeva 1, M.F. Joubert 2, and Y. Guyot 2; St. Petersburg National Research Univ. ITMO, 1 Vavilov SOI, Russia; 2 Inst. Lumière Matière, Univ. Lyon, France

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p26

Novopashin Vladimir

High quality dielectric coatings for solid-state lasers and laser components

Vladimir V. Novopashin, Aleksandr V. Shestakov; RDI Polyus, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p27

Zhao Wen

Under sampled target range Estimation in 3D Flash imaging ladar

Wen Zhao, Shaokun Han; School of Optoelectronics, Beijing Institute of Technology; P.R. China

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p28

Swiderski Jacek

Gain-Switched Tm-doped Fiber Laser and Amplifier with Simultaneous Mode-Locked- Like Operation

Jacek Swiderski, Maria Michalska, Lukasz Galecki, Wieslaw Pichola, Jacek Kwiatkowski, and Marcin Mamajek; Institute of Optoelectronics, Military University of Technology; Poland

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p29

Kwiatkowski Jacek

High repetition rate Q-switched Ho:YLF laser pumped by Tm: fiber laser

J. Kwiatkowski, W.Zendzian, J.K. Jabczynski, M. Kaskow, L. Gorajek; Military University of Technology, Poland

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p30

Kuznetsov Sergei A.

A highly efficient compact Yb:KYW laser

Sergei A. Kuznetsov, Victor S. Pivtsov; Institute of Laser Physics SB RAS, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p31

Kaskow Mateusz

Diode-side-pumped, Nd:YVO4 slab laser with four-wave mixing resonator
Mateusz Kaskow, Waldemar Zendzian, Lukasz Gorajek, Lukasz Galecki, Jacek Kwiatkowski, Michal Piasecki, Krzysztof Kopczynski, Jan K. Jabczynski;
Military University of Technology, Poland

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p32

Kaskow Mateusz

Investigations of room temperature, diode-side-pumped Yb:LuAG slab laser
Mateusz Kaskow 1, Lukasz Gorajek 1, Lukasz Galecki 1, Michal Piasecki 1, Jacek Kwiatkowski 1, Waldemar Zendzian 1, Krzysztof Kopczynski 1, Jan K. Jabczynski 1; Helena Jelinkova 2, Jan Sulc 2, Michal Nemec 2; 1 Institute of Optoelectronics, Military University of Technology, Poland; Faculty of Nuclear Physics and Physical Electronics, Czech Technical University, Czech Republic

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p33

Davtian Arsen

Passive Q-switched Nd:YAG single-frequency laser with tunable pulse shape and pulse duration
V. Pokrovsky, S. Terekhov, S. Sobolev, A. Davtian; Vavilov State Optical Institute, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p34

Sobolev Sergei

3 mJ@3.3 kHz single mode single-frequency end pumped pulsed Nd:YAG ring laser
A.S. Davtian, Z. V. Gorelova, V.P. Pokrovskiy, S.S. Sobolev, S.S. Terekhov; Vavilov State Optical Institute, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p35

Balmashnov Roman Vladimirovich

A modern CW DPSS-laser for Raman spectrometric method of wood identification
Roman V. Balmashnov, National Research University ITMO, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p36

Vitkin Vladimir

Robust eye-safe compact laser
Vadim M. Polyakov 1, Vladimir V. Vitkin 1, Vyacheslav A. Buchenkov 2, Andrey U. Rodionov 2; 1 National Research University ITMO, 2 Vavilov State Optical Institute, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p37

Smetanin Sergei

Numerical Simulation of a Passive Q-Switching Operation of the Diode-Pumped Solid-State Laser with a Multiloop Self-Phase-Conjugate Cavity
M.N. Ershkov 1, A.Yu. Vasiliev 1, S.N. Smetanin 2, A.V. Fedin 1, V.F. Lebedev 3, A.P. Pogoda 3, A.S. Boreysho 3; 1 Kovrov State Technological Academy; 2 General Physics Institute RAS; 3 Baltic State Technical University, Laser Systems LTD, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: WeR1-p38

Lobanov A.N.

Laser parameters measuring devices
A.N. Lobanov, O.V. Chesnokova; «Electrosteklo Ltd»; Russia

Session: R2. High Power Laser Systems and Facilities

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Wednesday, July 2

14:30-15:00 Code: WeR2-23, Invited

Kodymova Jarmila

Oxygen-Iodine lasers: advanced related technologies for pumping
Jarmila Kodymová; Institute of Physics, Academy of Sciences CR, Czech Republic

15:00-15:30 Code: WeR2-01, Invited

Kim Guang-Hoon

High peak and high average power Yb:KGW laser systems for industrial applications
G.H. Kim1, J. Yang1, S.A. Chizov1, A.V. Kulik1, E.G. Sall1, V.E. Yashin2, U. Kang1; 1 Korea Electrotechnology Research Institute, Republic of Korea; 2 Vavilov State Optical Institute, Russia

15:30-16:00 Code: WeR2-02, Invited

Zhdanov Boris

Alkali vapor lasers: history, current state and perspectives
B.V. Zhdanov, Randall J. Knize; USAF Academy, USA

16:00-16:30 Code: WeR2-03, Invited

Kotkov Andrey

Short Pulse CO Laser Systems and their Applications in Nonlinear IR Optics
A.A. Kotkov, A.A. Ionin, I.O. Kinyaevskiy, Yu.M. Klimachev, A.Yu. Kozlov; Lebedev Physical Institute RAS , Russia

16:30-17:00 Code: WeR2-04, Invited

Yuriev Michail
Optical (solar) pumped oxygen - iodine laser
M.S. Yur'ev, O.B. Danilov, A.P. Zhevlakov; Vavilov State Optical Institute, Russia

Wednesday, July 2

17:30-18:00 Code: WeR2-05, Invited

Mukhin Ivan
High repetition rate cryogenic disk laser for OPCPA applications
I. Mukhin; Institute of Applied Physics RAS, Russia

18:00-18:30 Code: WeR2-06, Invited

Shaykin Andrey
Space-to-time pulse shaping in the high energy high efficiency solid state laser amplifiers
A. Shaykin; Institute of Applied Physics, Russia

18:30-19:00 Code: WeR2-07, Invited

Palashov Oleg V.
Faraday isolators for high (>1kW) average power lasers
Oleg V. Palashov ; Institute of Applied Physics RAS; Russia

19:00-19:30 Code: WeR2-08

Churkin Dmitry
Pulsed inductive discharge HF laser
A. Razhev 1,2, D. Churkin 1,2, E. Kargapol'tsev 1; 1 Institute of Laser Physics SB RAS; 2 Novosibirsk State University; Russia

Thursday, July 3

15:00-15:15 Code: Thr2-09

Derkach Vladimir
Research on Luch facility in increasing of the pressure developed in laser experiments
S.A. Belkov, A.Yu. Voronin, I.N. Voronich, S.G. Garanin, S.Yu. Golovkin, S.Yu. Guskov1, N.N. Demchenko1, V.N. Derkach, N.V. Zmitrenko2, V.M. Izgorodin, N.A. Kudashева, V.B. Rozanov1, K.V. Starodubtsev, A.E. Chaunin; RFNC - VNIIEF, 1 Lebedev Physical Institute, 2 Keldysh Institute of Applied Mathematics RAS, Russia

15:15-15:30 Code: Thr2-10

Gao Yan-qi
Status of the SG-II-UP Laser Facility
Yan-qi Gao 1, Wei-xin Ma 1, Zhao-dong Cao 1, Jian Zhu 1, Xue-dong Yang 1, Ya-ping Dai 1, Bao-Qiang Zhu 1, Zun-qi Lin 2; 1 Shanghai Institute of Laser Plasma, 2 Shanghai Institute of Optics and Fine Mechanics; P.R. China

15:30-15:45 Code: Thr2-11

Xu Guang
Recent Status of the Petawatt Laser Facility for SG-II Upgrade Program
Guang Xu, Tao Wang, Zhaoyang Li, Dawei Li, Neng Hua, Jianwei Yu, Xuchun Li, Jian Zhu, Yaping Dai, Zunqi Lin, and Jianqiang Zhu; Shanghai Institute of Optics and Fine Mechanics, Chinese Academy of Sciences; P.R. China

15:45-16:00 Code: Thr2-12

Churkin Dmitry
Simultaneous generation of laser radiation at 337.1 nm and Lewis-Rayleigh afterglow in inductive nitrogen laser
A. Razhev 1,2, D. Churkin 1,2, E. Kargapol'tsev 1; 1 Institute of Laser Physics SB RAS; 2 Novosibirsk State University; Russia

16:00-16:15 Code: Thr2-13

Perevezentsev Evgeny
High Power Cryogenic Yb:YAG Disk Laser with Nanosecond Output Pulse Duration
E. A. Perevezentsev, I. B. Mukhin, O. V. Palashov, I. I. Kuznetsov, O. L. Vadimova; The Institute of Applied Physics RAS; Russia

16:15-16:30 Code: Thr2-14

Wang Zhen-guo
Time multiplexing technology for laser amplifier based on Yb-doped materials
Ming-zhong Li, Xiong-Jun Zhang, Zhen-guo Wang, Jian-gang Zheng, Xin-ying Jiang, Xiong-wei Yan, Min Li, Jun Zhang, Deng-sheng Wu, Qi-hua Zhu, Jing-qin Su, Kui-xing Zheng, Dong-xia Hu, Xiao-min Zhang; Research Center of Laser Fusion, Mianyang, China; P.R. China

16:30-16:45 Code: Thr2-15

Vadimova Olga

Specificities of laser pulse amplification in multi-pass amplifiers
Olga Vadimova, Ivan Mukhin, Oleg Palashov; 1 Institute of Applied Physics RAS, Russia

16:45-17:00 Code: ThR2-16

Khasenov Mendykhan

Mechanisms of population of the levels in some gas lasers pumped by ionizing radiation
M.U. Khasenov; Nazarbayev University Research and Innovation System, Kazakhstan; Austria

Thursday, July 3

17:30-17:45 Code: ThR2-17

Ma Pengfei

600 Watt-Level All-Fiber Polarization-Maintained Fiber Amplifier with
Pengfei Ma, Rumao Tao, Yanxing Ma, Xiaolin Wang, Rongtao Su, Pu Zhou; National University of Defense Technology; P.R. China

17:45-18:00 Code: ThR2-18

Nicolle Olivier

Multi-Petawatt Pulse Compression Gratings

A. Cotel 1, A. Liard 1, Y. Bernard 1, F. Desserouer 1, J-L. Domanchin 2; 1 HORIBA Jobin Yvon SAS, France; 2 HORIBA Jobin Yvon, Representative office, Russia

18:00-18:15 Code: ThR2-20

Starobor Aleksey

Double Channel Faraday Isolator with Single Optical Element for High-power Unpolarized Lasers

A.V. Starobor, D.S. Zheleznov, O.V. Palashov; Institute of Applied Physics RAS; Russia

18:15-18:30 Code: ThR2-21

Zhang Xiongjun

Progress of large-aperture plasma Pockels cell for high power laser in CAEP

Zhang Xiongjun, Li Mingzhong, Wu Dengsheng, Zhang Jun, Lin Donghui, Zheng Jianguang, Zheng Kuixing ; Research center of laser fusion, China academy of engineering physics; P.R. China

18:30-18:45 Code: ThR2-22

Zhu Meiping

Development of high performance optical coatings for laser systems

Meiping Zhu, Kui Yi, Hongji Qi, Weili Zhang, Yuanan Zhao, Jianda Shao ; Shanghai Institute of Optics and Fine Mechanics, Chinese Academy of Sciences; P.R. China

Poster presentations

Thursday, July 3

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR2-p01

Derkach I.N.

Optical specification and control of elements at UFL-2M laser facility

S.A. Belkov, I.N. Voronich, I.N. Derkach, A.A. Yerebin, I.E. Chernov; RFNC-VNIIEF, Russia; RFNC-VNIIEF

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR2-p02

Voronov Alexander

Numerical modeling of the optical system of UFL-2M laser facility

S.A. Belkov 1, I.N. Voronich 1, A.L. Voronov 1, N.A. Voronina 1, I.N. Derkach 1, I.V.Epatko 2, R.V. Serov 2, N.A. Filatova 1, I.E. Chernov 1; 1 RFNC-VNIIEF, 2 General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR2-p03

Zubkov Anton

The efficiency research of radiation energy conversion to the third harmonic for "Iskra 5" iodine laser

V.E. Gaganov, S.V. Kalipanov, V.P. Kovalenko, S.P. Kurnopyalov, V.S. Fayzullin, A.V. Zubkov; Russian Federal NuclearCentre 'All-Russian Scientific Research Institute of Experimental Physics' (VNIIEF), Research Institute of Laser Physics

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR2-p04

Mineev Aleksandr

Experimental Study on Operation at Room Temperature of RF Excited Planar CO- Laser

A. P. Mineev 1, S. M. Nefedov 1, P. P. Pashinin 1, P. A. Goncharov 1, V. V. Kiselev 1, V.B. Shuvalov 2; 1 A.M. Prokhorov General Physics Institute RAS; 2 National Research Nuclear University;; Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR2-p05

Mineev Aleksandr

Radio Frequency Excited Planar Inert Gas Mixture Infrared Lasers

A. P. Mineev 1, S. M. Nefedov 1, P. P. Pashinin 1, P. A. Goncharov 1, V. V. Kiselev 1, V.B. Shuvalov 2; 1 General Physics Institute RAS, 2

National Research Nuclear University; Russia.

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR2-p06

Petrov V.V.

Implementation of Multiterawatt Femtosecond Laser System at Kilohertz Repetition Rate

V.V. Petrov, A.V. Laptev, E.V. Pestryakov, G.V. Kuptsov, V.A. Petrov, S.A. Frolov, V.I. Trunov, A.V. Kirpichnikov; Institute of Laser Physics SB RAS, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR2-p07

Chernov Ilya

Research in effect of optical elements inhomogeneity on a spatial distribution of laser radiation on laser facility Luch

S.A. Bel'kov 1, O.A. Buchirina 1, N.A. Voronina 1, I.N. Voronich 1, I.N. Derkach 1, V.N. Derkach 1, A.A. Eremin 1, I.V.Epatko 2, R.V. Serov 2, D.V. Sizmin 1, N.A. Filatova 1, I.E. Chernov 1; 1 RFNC-VNIIEF, 2 General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR2-p08

Danilevichius Rokas

Reduction of Third Order Dispersion Mismatch Between Fiber Stretcher and Grating Compressor by Using Split-Second-Grating Compressor Design

R. Danilevicius, J. Zeludevicius, K. Viskontas, N. Rusteika, K. Regelskis; Center for Physical Sciences & Technology, Lithuania

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR2-p09

Frankinas Saulius

High Power Femtosecond CPA System With TOD Compensating Chirped Fiber Bragg Grating Stretcher

Saulius Frankinas, Rokas Danilevicius, Nerijus Rusteika; Institute of Physics, Lithuania

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR2-p11

Shakir Yury

Kinetics of Er 3+ Emission under Laser-thermal Excitation of Er2O3

V.M.Marchenko, Yu.A.Shakir; General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR2-p12

Tabet Saida

Study Of The Temperature Distribution In Diode-End-Pumped Solid State- Lasers

Tabet Saida, Lakhdari Fouad, Osmani Ismahen, Khammar Messouda; Centre for Development of Advanced Technologies (CDTA) . Unit of Research in Optics and Photonics (UROP); Algeria

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR2-p13

Tao Rumao

Theoretical Study of High Power Mode Instabilities in 2µm Thulium-Doped Fiber Amplifiers

Rumao Tao, Pu Zhou, Hu Xiao, Xiaolin Wang, Zejin Liu; National University of Defense Technology, China; P.R. China

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR2-p14

Zeludevicius Julijanas

Performance of Nonlinear Ultra-Short Pulse Fiber CPA System Using Power Amplifiers with Core Diameter from 12 to 33 µm

J. Želudevicius, R. Danilevicius, K. Viskontas, N. Rusteika, K. Regelskis; Center for Physical Sciences & Technology, Lithuania

Session: R3. Semiconductor Lasers, Materials and Applications

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Tuesday, July 1

09:00-09:30 Code: TuR3-01, Invited

Marsh John

Mode-Locked Semiconductor Lasers: from Giga-Hertz to Tera-Hertz

John H. Marsh and Lianping Hou ; School of Engineering, University of Glasgow; UK

09:30-10:00 Code: TuR3-02, Invited

Asryan Levon V.

Intradot Relaxation and Modulation Bandwidth in Quantum Dot Lasers

Levon V. Asryan 1, Yuchang Wu 1, Robert A. Suris 2; 1 Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, USA; 2 Ioffe Physical Technical Institute RAS, Russia;

10:00-10:30 Code: TuR3-03, Invited

Danckaert Jan

Dynamics of semiconductor ring lasers and its applications

J. Danckaert, R.M. Nguimdo, M. Khoder, L. Mashal, W. Coomans, S. Kingni Takougang, L. Gelens, G. Van der Sande, G. Verschaffelt; Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Belgium

10:30-10:45 Code: TuR3-04

Viktorov Evgeniy

Dynamical interplay between ground and excited states in quantum dot laser

G.S.Sokolovskii 1, V.V.Dudelev 1, E.D.Kolykhalova 2, A.G.Deryagin 1, A. Bakoz 3, I.I.Novikov 1, M.V.Maximov 1, A.E.Zhukov 4, V.M.Ustinov 1, V.I.Kuchinskii 1, W.Sibbett 5, E.U.Rafailov 6, E.A.Viktorov 3,7, T.Erneux 7; 1 Ioffe Physical-Technical Institute, 2 St. Petersburg State Electrotechnical University "LETI", 3 National Research University ITMO, 4 Academic University, Russia; 5 University of St Andrews, 6 Aston University, UK; 7 Univerite libre de Bruxelles, Belgium

10:45-11:00 Code: TuR3-05

Kelleher Bryan

Dynamics of frequency swept sources

B. Kelleher 1,2, S. Slepneva 1,2, B. O'Shaughnessy 1,2, S.P. Hegarty 2, A. Vladimirov 3, G. Huyet 1,2; 1 Cork Institute of Technology, 2 University College Cork, Ireland; 3 Weierstrass Institute for Applied Analysis and Stochastics, Germany

Tuesday, July 1

11:30-12:00 Code: TuR3-07, Invited

Suedmeyer Thomas

Using SESAMs as fast opto-optical modulators for low-noise CEO stabilization of ultrafast lasers

Stéphane Schilt, Martin Hoffmann, Thomas Südmeyer; Université de Neuchâtel, Switzerland

12:00-12:30 Code: TuR3-06, Invited

Rode Andrei

Experimental Observation for New Polymorphs of Silicon Formed through Ultrafast- Laser-Induced Microexplosion

L. Rapp(1), B. Haberl(2), Chris Pickard(3) J. E. Bradby(2), E. G. Gamaly(1), J. S. Williams(2), A. V. Rode(1) ; (1,2) The Australian National University, (3) Department of Physics and Astronomy, University College London, UK

12:30-12:45 Code: TuR3-08

Chamorovskiy Alexander

Semiconductor lasers with fast broadband tuning in 750-1100 nm spectral range

M.V. Shramenko 1, A.Yu.Chamorovskiy 1, A.A. Lobintsov 1, S.D. Yakubovich 2; 1 Superlum, Cork, Ireland; Superlum Moscow, Russia; 2 MSTU MIREA, Russia

12:45-13:00 Code: TuR3-09

Chizhevsky Vyacheslav

200 Mbps Real-time True Random Bit Generator Based on Polarization Noise in a VCSEL

V.N. Chizhevsky 1, A.S. Maloshtan 1, A.V. Glejm 2; 1 B.I. Stepanov Institute of Physics NAS Belarus, Belarus, 2 National Research University ITMO, Quantum Communications Ltd, Russia

13:00-13:15 Code: TuR3-10

Danilov Leonid

Optimization of laser heterostructures for mid-infrared

L.V. Danilov, G.G. Zegrya; Ioffe Physical Technical Institute RAS, Russia

13:15-13:30 Code: TuR3-11

Slipchenko Sergey

Epitaxially intergrated power efficient switch for high power laser pulse generation in semiconductor heterostructures of 900 nm wavelength

S.O. Slipchenko1, A.A. Podoskin1, A.V. Rozhkov1, N.A. Pikhtin1, I.S. Tarasov1, T.A. Bagaev2, M.V. Zverkov2, V.P. Konyaev2, Y.V. Kurniavko2, M.A. Ladugin2, A.A. Marmalyuk2, A.A. Padalitsa2, V.A. Simakov2; 1 Ioffe Physical Technical Institute RAS; 2 RDI "Polyus", Russia

Tuesday, July 1

15:00-15:30 Code: TuR3-12, Invited

Ivanov Sergey

II-VI/III-N based micro-chip green-yellow laser converters

S.V. Ivanov 1, S.V. Sorokin 1, S.V. Gronin 1, I.V. Sedova 1, A.G. Vainilovich 2, E.V. Lutsenko 2; 1 Ioffe Physical Technical Institute RAS, Russia; 2 Stepanov Institute of Physics of NAS, Belarus

15:30-16:00 Code: TuR3-13, Invited

Laurell Fredrik

Nonlinear optics with diode lasers

F. Laurell, KTH, Sweden

16:00-16:15 Code: TuR3-14

Fedorova Ksenia A.

73 nm wavelength tuning from a frequency-doubled quantum-dot laser in PPKTP waveguides

Ksenia A. Fedorova 1,2; Grigorii S. Sokolovskii 2; Phillip R. Battle 3; Daniil A. Livshits 4; Edik U. Rafailov 1; 1 Aston University, UK, 2 Ioffe Physical Technical Institute RAS, Russia; 3 AdvR Inc, USA; 4 Innolume GmbH, Germany;

16:15-16:30 Code: TuR3-15

Titkov Ilya

Novel Evaluation Procedure for Internal and Extraction Efficiency of High-Power Blue LEDs

I.E. Titkov¹, A. Yadav¹, V.L. Zeroval¹, M. Zulonasl¹ E.U. Rafailov¹; S.Yu. Karpov²; M. Strassburg³, I. Pietzonka³, H.-J. Lugauer³, B. Galler³; ¹ Aston University, UK; ² STR Group - Soft-Impact Ltd, Russia; ³ Novel Technologies, Germany

16:30-16:45 Code: TuR3-16

Rantamaki Antti

Semiconductor disk laser with a semiconductor-dielectric-metal mirror

Antti Rantamäki, Esa J. Saarinen, Jari Lyytikäinen, Kimmo Lahtonen, Mika Valden, and Oleg G. Okhotnikov; Optoelectronics Research Centre, Tampere University of Technology; Finland

16:45-17:00 Code: TuR3-17

Zubov Fedor

Improvement of light-current characteristic linearity in a quantum well laser with asymmetric barriers

F.I. Zubov¹, A.E. Zhukov¹, Yu.M. Shernyakov¹, M.V. Maximov¹, N.V. Kryzhanovskaya¹, L.V. Asryan², E.S. Semenova³, K. Yvind³; ¹ St. Petersburg Academic University, Russia; ² Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, USA**Tuesday, July 1**

17:30-18:00 Code: TuR3-19, Invited

Okhotnikov Oleg G.

Towards THz-Class Pulse Train Semiconductor Disk Lasers

Oleg G. Okhotnikov and Esa J. Saarinen; Optoelectronics Research Centre, Tampere University of Technology; Finland

18:00-18:30 Code: TuR3-20, Invited

Vitiello Miriam Serena

Engineering Quantum Cascade Lasers as single-mode, regular beam profile and narrow-linewidth source across the far-infrared

M.S. Vitiello, NEST, CNR - Istituto Nanoscienze and Scuola Normale Superiore, Italy

18:30-18:45 Code: TuR3-21

Gorodetsky Andrei

Quantum Dot-Based Terahertz Photoconductive Antennas

A. Gorodetsky¹, R.R. Leyman², E.U. Rafailov¹; ¹ Aston University, ² University of Glasgow, UK**Thursday, July 3**

09:30-10:00 Code: ThR3-23, Invited

Rahimi-Iman Arash

Electrically Driven Polaritonic Lasing

Arash Rahimi-Iman; Philipps-Universität Marburg, Germany

10:00-10:30 Code: ThR3-24, Invited

Hogg Richard

All-Semiconductor Photonic Crystal Surface Emitting Lasers.

R. J. E. Taylor¹, D.M. Williams¹, D.T. D. Childs¹, P.S. Ivanov¹, K.M. Groom¹, L. Shepherd¹, A. J. Crombie¹, P.Ivanov¹, B.J. Stevens¹, S. Khamas¹, R.A. Hogg¹, N. Ikeda², and Y. Sugimoto²; ¹ Department of Electronic & Electrical Engineering, University of Sheffield, UK; ² Nanotechnology Innovation Center, National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS), Japan

10:30-10:45 Code: ThR3-25

Jaurigue Lina

Impact of amplitude-phase coupling on optical feedback induced timing jitter reduction in passively mode-locked lasers

Lina Jaurigue, Kathy Lüdge and Eckehard Schöll; Institute of Theoretical Physics Technical University Berlin, Germany

10:45-11:00 Code: ThR3-26

Rahimi-Iman Arash

Evolution of multi-mode emission from vertical-external-cavity surface-emitting lasers

M. Wichmann¹, M. K. Shakfa¹, B. Heinen¹, A. Rahimi-Iman¹, S. W. Koch^{1,2}, M. Koch¹, M. Scheller², J. V. Moloney²; ¹ Philipps-Universität Marburg, Germany; ² The University of Arizona, USA**Thursday, July 3**

11:30-12:00 Code: ThR3-27, Invited

Malcolm Graeme

Novel Narrow Linewidth & Ultrafast Solid State & Semiconductor Disk Lasers

G. Malcolm; M Squared Lasers, UK

12:00-12:30 Code: ThR3-28, Invited

Resan Bojan

High Pulse Repetition Rate Lasers Modelocked with Quantum Dot SESAMs
Bojan Resan; Time-Bandwidth Products AG, Switzerland

12:30-12:45 Code: ThR3-29

Ilchenko Stepan

Spatially single-mode reliable superluminescent diodes with CW output power of up to 100 mW
S.N. Il'chenko 1, Yu.O. Kostin 1, S.D. Yakubovich 2; 1 SUPERLUM DIODES Ltd., 2 MSTU MIREA; Russia

12:45-13:00 Code: ThR3-30

Ilchenko Stepan

SLD-based light-emitting modules at 1300 nm operable in temperature range from - 55°C to +125°C
S. N. Ilchenko 1, Yu. O. Kostin 1, S. D. Yakubovich 2 ; 1 SUPERLUM DIODES Ltd., 2 MSTU MIREA; Russia

13:00-13:15 Code: ThR3-31

Hann Swook

Low-cost Multimodal Analyzer on Wavelength and Power Measurement

Swook Hann 1, Young-Eun Im 1, Yune Hyoum Kim 1, Seon-Ju Kim 2; 1 Korea Photonics Technology Institute, 2 LS Tech Co., Ltd.

13:15-13:30 Code: ThR3-32

Guo Linhui

High brightness and power fiber coupled diode laser based on multiple beam combining technologies

Guo Linhui, Yu Junhong, Wang Zhao, Tan Hao, Gao Songxin, Wu Deyong, Zhang Kai; The Key Laboratory of Science and Technology on High Energy Laser, Institute of Applied Electronics, CAEP, P.R.China; P.R. China

Poster presentations

Thursday, July 3

15:00-19:30 Code: ThR3-p01

Bokhan P.A.

Lasing peculiarities of compounds AlxGal-xN at pumping up with electron beams and UV radiation of the second harmonics of copper vapor laser
P.A. Bokhan, Dm.E. Zakrevsky, V.A. Kim, K.S. Zhuravlev, T.V. Malin, I.V. Osinnykh; Institute of Semiconductor Physics SB RAS; Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: ThR3-p02

Bokhan Petr

Investigation of lasers generation characteristics in compounds ZnS, CdS, ZnSe at pumping up with the electron beam generated in an open discharge

P.A. Bokhan, Dm.E. Zakrevsky, P.P. Gugin, V.I. Solomonov, A.V. Spirina; 1 Institute of Semiconductor Physics SB RAS, 2 Institute of Electrophysics, Ural Branch RAS, Russia; Institute of Semiconductor Physics SB RAS

15:00-19:30 Code: ThR3-p03

Bochkova Elena

Active mode locking in laser gyroscope on semiconductor optical amplifiers and long fiber cavity

Yu. Yu. Broslavets, V.P. Duraev, A.A. Fomichev; Moscow Institute of Physics and Technology (State University), Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: ThR3-p04

Gorlachuk Pavel

High power 1550 nm Multijunction Laser Emitters Based On Integrated Heterostructure

P. Gorlachuk, I. Yarotskaya, Yu. Ryaboshtan, M. Ladugin, A. Padalitsa, A. Marmalyuk, A. Ivanov, V. Kurnosov, K. Kurnosov, O. Zhuravleva, R. Chernov and V. Romantsevich, A. Lobintsov, V. Simakov; Polyus R&D Institute; Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: ThR3-p05

Bagaev Timur

Triple-wavelength Laser Diodes Based on Epitaxially Stacked AlGaAs/GaAs Heterostructures

T. Bagaev, A. Padalitsa, A. Marmalyuk, M. Ladugin, I. Yarotskaya, A. Lobintsov, S. Sapozhnikov, E. Davydova, A. Morozyuk, V. Konyaev, V. Simakov; Polyus R&D; Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: ThR3-p06

Koryukin I.V.

Relaxation Oscillations in a Quantum Dot Laser

I.V. Koryukin; Institute of Applied Physics RAS; Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: ThR3-p07

Morozov Yuri

Operational Characteristics of Intracavity Singly-Resonant Optical Parametric Oscillator Pumped by Vertical External Cavity Surface-Emitting Laser

Yu.A. Morozov 1, M.Yu. Morozov 1, V. I. Kozlovsky 2, O. Okhotnikov 3; 1 Kotelnikov Inst. of radioEng. & Electr. RAS (Saratov Branch), 2 P.N. Lebedev Physical Inst. RAS, Russia; 3 Optoelectronics Research Centre, Finland

15:00-19:30 Code: ThR3-p08

Zverev M.M.

The effect of mercury lamp irradiation on the threshold current density of electron beam pumped ZnSe-based lasers

M.M. Zverev1, N.A. Gamov1, E.V. Zhdanov1, D.V. Peregoudov1, V.B. Studionov1, S.V. Gronin2, I.V. Sedova2, S.V. Sorokin2, S.V. Ivanov 2; 1 Moscow State Technical University (MIREA), 2 Ioffe Physical Technical Institute RAS, Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: ThR3-p09

Zverev M.M.

Pulsed Electron Beam Pumped Laser Based on ZnCdSe MQW Structure With High Threshold of Catastrophic Degradation

M.M. Zverev1, N.A. Gamov1, E.V. Zhdanov1, D.V. Peregoudov1, V.B. Studionov1, S.V. Gronin2, I.V. Sedova2, S.V. Sorokin2, S.V. Ivanov2; 1 Moscow State Technical University (MIREA), 2 Ioffe Physical Technical Institute RAS, Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: ThR3-p10

Utkin Andrei B.

Compact Autonomous LIDAR for Fire and Intrusion Detection

Andrei B. Utkin, Fernando Piedade, Vasco Beixiga, Pedro Mota and Pedro Lousa; INOV - INESC Inovação and ICEMS IST, Technical University of Lisbon, Portugal

Session: R4. Laser Beam Control

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Tuesday, July 1

15:00-15:30 Code: TuR4-01, Invited

Bonora Stefano

Adaptive optics for pulse shaping and image optimization

S. Bonora, Institute of Nanotechnologies and Photonics, Italy

15:30-16:00 Code: TuR4-02, Invited

Artal Pablo

Adaptive optics: the future of visual testing

Pablo Artal; Universidad de Murcia, Spain

16:00-16:30 Code: TuR4-03, Invited

Reinlein Claudia

Thermal-piezoelectric deformable mirror (TPDM) for high power lasers

Claudia Reinlein, Michael Appelfelder; Fraunhofer Institute of Applied Optics and Precision Engineering, IOF, Germany

16:30-17:00 Code: TuR4-04, Invited

Kudryashov Alexis

Closed loop adaptive system with Hartmann wavefront sensor for CO2 laser radiation correction

Alexis Kudryashov 1, Alex Alexandrov 1, Vadim Samarkin 1, Alexey Rukosuev 1, Pierre Galarneau 2; 1 Moscow University of Mechanical Engineering, Russia; 2 INO, Canada

Tuesday, July 1

17:30-17:45 Code: TuR4-05

Chetkin Sergey

Experimental and theoretical study of thin plate uniform, bimorph and membrane adaptive mirrors, which reflecting surface is under deformable control by piezoceramic and magnetostrictive actuators

S.A.Chetkin 1. A.B.Egorov 1, A.G.Safronov 2; 1 General Physics Institute RAS; 2 New Energy Technologies LLC, Russia

17:45-18:00 Code: TuR4-06

Galaktionov Ilya

Phase correction of laser beam passed through turbid medium

I. Galaktionov, J. Sheldakova, A. Kudryashov; Moscow State University of Mechanical Engineering, Russia

18:00-18:30 Code: TuR4-07, Invited

Villoresi Paolo

Turbulence as a resource in Quantum Communications

Giuseppe Vallone, Alberto Dall'Arche, Davide Bacco, Davide Marangon, Marco Tomasin, Francesca Gerlin, Matteo Canale, Nicola Laurenti, and Paolo Villoresi; University of Padova, Italy

18:30-19:00 Code: TuR4-08, Invited

Forbes Andrew

The digital laser
A. Forbes, National Laser Centre, South Africa

19:00-19:15 Code: TuR4-09

Hu Yun
Gain Controlling Method Based on Electro-Optical Switch for ASE Suppression of Excimer Laser
Yun Hu, Xueqing Zhao, Dahui Wang, Yongxiang Zhu, Yongsheng Zhang; Northwest Institute of Nuclear Technology, China; P.R. China

19:15-19:30 Code: TuR4-10

Wang Dahui
Automatic alignment of angularly multiplexed beams in excimer laser MOPA system
Dahui Wang, Hang Qian, Lianying Ma, Xueqing Zhao, Yongsheng Zhang, Gang Feng, Bibo Shao, Aiping Yi, Jun Zhao; Northwest Institute of Nuclear Technology, China; P.R. China

Thursday, July 3

09:00-09:30 Code: ThR4-11

Lukin V.P.
Efficiency of adaptive correction application for laser beam formation in atmosphere with the use of incoherent images as reference
V.P. Lukin ; Institute of Atmospheric Optics SB RAS; Russia

09:30-09:45 Code: TuR4-12

Malashko Ya.I.
High precision adaptive auto-focusing system for laser beam based on method of double frequency of the spherical wave front probe.
A.N. Kleymentov, Ya.I. Malashko, A.V. Nazarenko, A.O. Skvortsov; MSDB "Almaz-Antey", Russia

09:45-10:00 Code: TuR4-13

Malashko Ya.I.
Method of laser angular divergence measurement by reflected signal from distant point object
S. I. Krisanov, Ya.I. Malashko, A.V. Nazarenko, P.A. Morgunov; MSDB "Almaz-Antey"; Russia

10:00-10:15 Code: ThR4-14

Semenov Peter A.
Active Coherent Combining Method Based on Multi-aperture Wave Front Sensors
S.D. Pol'skikh, P.A. Semenov; National center of laser systems and complexes "Astrophysics"; Russia

10:15-10:30 Code: ThR4-15

Venediktov Vladimir
Magnification of Interferogram with the Use of Digital Holography
Vladimir Ivanov 1, Sergey Pul'kin 1, Alexander Sevryugin 2, and Vladimir Venediktov 1,2; 1 St.-Petersburg State Electrotechnical University "LETI", 2 St.-Petersburg State University, Russia

10:30-10:45 Code: ThR4-16

Geng Chao
New applications of Adaptive Fiber-Optics Collimator in Fiber Coupling and Beam Pointing
Chao Geng, Xinyang Li, Wen Luo, Yi Tan, Hongmei Liu, and Jinbo Mu; Institute of Optics and Electronics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China; P.R. China

10:45-11:00 Code: ThR4-17

Li Xinyang
Research Progress on Beam Combining of Fiber Amplifiers in IOE, CAS
Xinyang Li, Chao Geng, Wen Luo, Yi Tan, Hongmei Liu, and Jinbo Mu; Institute of Optics and Electronics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China; P.R. China

Thursday, July 3

11:30-12:00 Code: ThR4-18, Invited

Soskin Marat
Topology of laser beams.
M. Soskin, V. Vasil'ev; Institute of Physics NAS Ukraine, Ukraine;

12:00-12:15 Code: ThR4-19

Rodin Aleksej
Investigation of Beam Quality in Nd:YAG Crystal Fiber Amplifier
A. Rodin 1, A. Dement'ev 1, D. Brickus 1, K. Sasnauskas 1, A. Michailovas 2, A. Aleknavicius 2, J. Didierjean 3; 1 Center for Physical Sciences and Technology, 2 Ekspla uab, Lithuania; 3 Fibercryst SAS, France; Lithuania

12:15-12:30 Code: ThR4-20

Stukachev Sergey

Experimental testing of the diffraction method for optical wavefield recording
S.E. Stukachev, I.E. Kozhevnikov; Institute of Applied Physics RAS; Russia

12:30-12:45 Code: Thr4-21

Popov Sergei

Tailored polarization eigenstates of liquid crystal SLM to generate Laguerre-Gaussian beams
M.Favier 1, S.Popov 2; 1 Inst. d'Optique, France, 2 Royal Inst. of Technology, Sweden

12:45-13:00 Code: Thr4-22

Brundavanam Maruthi Manoj

Polarization structure of an optical vortex beam near the unfolding point using a modified birefringent interferometer
M. M Brundavanam 1, Y. Miyamoto 2; 1 Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur, India, 2 University of Electro-Communications, Japan

13:00-13:30 Code: Thr4-23, Invited

Geints Yuri

Photonic Nanojets from Microspheres: A Step to Superfocusing of Light
Alexander A. Zemlyanov, Yuri E. Geints, Ekaterina K. Panina; V.E.Zuev Institute of Atmospheric Optics SB RAS, Russia

Thursday, July 3

15:00-15:15 Code: Thr4-24

Venus Georgiy

Novel laser cavity design by way of transmitting volume Bragg gratings
B. Anderson 1, I. Divliansky 1, L. Glebov 1, V. Smirnov 2, G. Venus 1; 1 University of Central Florida, 2 OptiGrate Corp., USA

15:15-15:30 Code: Thr4-25

Kokodii Nikolaj

Control of beam profile of high power laser by knife-edge mechanism
N.G. Kokodii 1,2, Li Zhenhua 1, M.V.Kaydash 2, V.A. Timanyuk 2; 1 V.N. Karazin Kharkov National University, 2 National University of Pharmacy; Ukraine

15:30-15:45 Code: Thr4-26

Zhang Li

Experimental investigation on aero-optic effects under laser irradiating
Zhang Li, Tao Yanhui, Wang Guibing, Liu Guodong, Wang Chunyan, Kuang Xuewu, Li Jianming, Liu Haitao, Gui Yangzhen; Institute of Fluid Physics, China; P.R. China

15:45-16:00 Code: Thr4-27

Wu Jing

Research on the beam cleanup of slab laser by one-dimensional arrangement deformable mirror
Wu Jing 1,2. Xiang Rujian 1,2. Li Guohui 1,2. Yang Yuan 1,2. He Zhongwu 1,2.; 1 Institute of Applied Electronics, CAEP, 2 Key Laboratory of Science and Technology on High Energy Laser, CAEP, China; P.R. China

16:00-16:30 Code: Thr4-28, Invited

Belfi Jacopo

Experimental activity toward GINGER (Gyroscopes IN General Relativity)
J. Belfi 1, F. Bosi 1, A. Di Virgilio 1, N. Beverini 2, G. Carelli 2, E. Maccioni 2, R. Santagata 3, D. Cuccato 4, A. Ortolan 5; 1 INFN, sezione di Pisa; 2 Univ. of Pisa; 3 Univ. of Siena; 4 Univ. of Padova; 5 INFN Legnaro; Italy

16:30-17:00 Code: Thr4-29, Invited

Beverini Nicolo

Ring Laser Gyroscope for accurate angle metrology
N. Beverini 1, G. Carelli 1, E. Maccioni 1, J. Belfi 2, A. Di Virgilio 2, M. Pisani 3, A. Ortolan 4; 1 Dipartimento di Fisica dell'Univ. di Pisa; 2 INFN-sezione de Pisa, 3 INRIM, 4 INFN Legnaro; Italy

Thursday, July 3

17:30-18:00 Code: Thr4-30, Invited

Chernykh Dmitriy

Gyroscopic effect in the bidirectional femtosecond erbium-doped fiber ring laser
Dmitriy Chernykh, Alexander Krylov; Fiber Optics Research Center RAS, Russia

18:00-18:30 Code: Thr4-31, Invited

Velikoseltsev Alexander

Precision Cavity Control for the Stable Operation of a Large Ring Laser Gyroscope
K. U. Schreiber 1, A. Gebauer 1, A. Velikoseltsev 2, J.-P. R. Wells 3; 1 Forschungseinrichtung Satellitengeodaesie Technische Universitaet Muenchen, Germany; 2 St. Petersburg Electrotechnical Univ.; 3 University of Canterbury, New Zealand; Russia

18:30-18:45 Code: Thr4-32

Venediktov Vladimir

On the Possibility of Phase Measurements in Microoptical Gyro

Yury V. Filatov 1, Egor V. Shalymov 1, and Vladimir Yu. Venediktov 1,2; 1 St.-Petersburg State Electrotechnical University "LETI", 2 St.-Petersburg State University, Russia

Poster presentations**Wednesday, July 2**

15:00-19:00 Code: WeR4-p01

Bubis E.L.

Contrast Inversion by Focusing Laser Beam in an Absorbing Medium

E.L. Bubis, V.V. Lozhkarev, I.E. Kozhevato, V.O. Martynov, D.E. Silin, A.N. Stepanov, S.A. Gusev*; Institute of Applied Physics RAS, * Institute for Physics of Microstructures RAS; Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: WeR4-p02

Khosrovian Gaik

Filled-aperture Coherent Summation Technique for Multiple High Average Power Laser Beams

G. Khosrovian 1, S. Taniguchi 1, M. Fujita 1, Y. Izawa 1, K. Tsubakimoto 2, H. Yoshida 2, N. Miyanaga 2; 1 Institute for Laser Technology, ALPROT, 2 Institute of Laser Engineering; Japan

15:00-19:00 Code: WeR4-p03

Angervaks Aleksandr

Holographic medium for the mid-IR narrow-band filters

A.S. Shcheulin, A.E. Angervaks, A.I. Ryskin; National Research University ITMO, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: WeR4-p04

Maslov Vyacheslav

Propagation and focusing of modes of the dielectric resonator of terahertz laser

O.V.Gurin, A.V.Degtyarev, V.A.Maslov, V.S.Senyuta, V.A.Svich, A.N.Topkov ; V.N.Karazin Kharkov National University, Department of the Quantum Radiophysics; Ukraine

15:00-19:00 Code: WeR4-p05

Kanev Feodor

Influence of distortions on quality of radiation generated by multichannel optical system

F. Kanev 1, E. Tsyro 1, O. Antipov 2; 1 V.E. Zuev Institute of Atmospheric Optics SB RAS, 2 Institute of Applied Physics RAS; Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: WeR4-p06

Trunov Vladimir

High-resolution Shack-Hartmann sensor for measuring variations of high-power laser beams

A.G. Poleshchuk 1, A.G. Sedukhin 1, V.V. Cherkashin 1, V.G. Maksimov 2, V.A. Tartakovskiy 2, V.I. Trunov 3; 1 Institute of Automation and Electrometry SB RAS, 2 Institute of monitoring climatic and ecological systems SB RAS, 3 Institute of Laser Physics SB RAS, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: WeR4-p07

Grishkanich Aleksandr

Optimization of structuring silicon-based thin film solar modules using means of laser scribing

D. N. Redkal, V.A. Parfenov1, V.P. Afanasjevl, A.V. Kukin1, F. S. Egorov3, A.S. Grishkanich1,2 1 St. Petersburg Electrotechnical University "LETI", 2 National Research University ITMO, 3 Chuvash State University, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: WeR4-p08

Feoktistov Vyacheslav

Interferometric measurements of optical inhomogeneities in an alkali vapor laser active medium

A.A. Babin, O.I. Beloshitskaya, V.A. Bogachev, S.G. Garanin, G.N. Kachalin, A.V. Kopalkin, S.M. Kulikov, A.S. Safronov, F.A. Starikov, S.A. Sukharev, V.V. Feoktistov, V.A. Shotniev; Russian Federal Nuclear Center, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: WeR4-p09

Sizmin Dmitry

Investigation of the laser beam smoothing system using optical waveguide

V.N. Derkach, D.V. Sizmin, P.V. Starodubtsev; RFNC - VNIIEF, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: WeR4-p10

Polukeev Eugen

Influence of Zeeman laser gyro optical circuit deformation on its drift.

Yu.Yu. Broslavets, E.A. Polukeev, A.A. Fomichev; Moscow Insitute of Physic and Technology, Russia.

15:00-19:00 Code: WeR4-p11

Mikhaylov Danil

Tilt corrector based on bimorph piezoelectric actuators

V.V. Kijko^{1,2}, A.G. Suzdal'tsev¹, D.A. Mikhaylov^{1, 2}; 1 General Physics Institute RAS; 2 National Research University ITMO, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: WeR4-p12

Sidoryuk Oleg

Formation of Predefined Microrelief of Optical Surface by Coating Deposition through Laser Pyrolysis of Organosilicon Vapor

A.Yu. Golyaeva¹, E.V. Dorofeeva², P.Yu. Lobanov¹, I.S. Manuylovich¹, O.E. Sidoryuk¹; 1. M. F. Stelmakh "Polyus" research institute; 2. M.M. Shemyakin and Yu.A. Ovchinnikov Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry RAS, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: WeR4-p13

Azarova Valentina

Sub-nano precision optical surfaces, thin films, heterostructures and laser mirrors

V. Azarova, T. Tsvetkova, V. Fokin; R&DI "Polyus", Russia; RDI "Polyus"

Session: R5. Super-Intense Light Fields and Ultra-Fast Processes

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Wednesday, July 2

09:00-09:30 Code: WeR5-01, Invited

Kalashnikov Mikhail

ELI-ALPS - unique European laser facility

D.Charalambidis^{1,2}, E.Cormier^{1,3}, Z. Divekil⁴, Jo.A. Fülöp^{1,5}, M. Kalashnikov^{1,6}, R. Lopez-Martens^{1,7}, K. Osvay^{1,8}, E. Raczi^{1,9}; 1 ELI-Hu Nkft, Hungary; 2 FORTH, Greece; 3 CELIA, France; 4 Imperial College, UK; 5 MTA-PTE High-Field THz Research Group, Pecs, Hungary; 6 Max-Born-Inst., Germany; 7 Lab. d'Optique Appliquee, France; 8 Univ. of Szeged, Hungary; 9 Obuda Univ., Hungary

09:30-10:00 Code: WeR5-02, Invited

Azechi Hiroshi

LFEX High Energy Peta-Watt Laser and Its Potential for High Field Science

H. Azechi; Institute of Laser Engineering, Osaka University, Japan

10:00-10:30 Code: WeR5-03, Invited

McKenna Paul

Ultraintense laser-plasma interactions in the relativistic transparency regime

P. McKenna¹, R.J. Gray¹, D.A. MacLellan¹, B. Gonzalez-Izquierdo¹, H.W. Powell¹, D.C. Carroll², C.D. Murphy³, L.C. Stockhausen⁴, D.R. Rusby^{1,2}, G.G. Scott^{1,2}, R. Wilson¹, N. Booth², D.R. Symes², S.J. Hawkes², R. Torres⁴, M. Borghesi⁵, D. Neely²; 1 University of Strathclyde, UK 2 STFC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, UK 3 University of Edinburgh, UK, 4 Centro de Laseres Pulsados (CLPU), Spain, 5 Queens University Belfast, UK

10:30-11:00 Code: WeR5-04, Invited

Nam Chang Hee

Laser Particle Acceleration at Relativistic Laser Intensity

Ch. H. Nam^{1,2}; J. Kim^{1,3}; H.T. Kim^{1,3}; K.H. Pael^{1,3}; W. Choi^{1,3}; Ch.M. Kim^{1,3}; S.K. Lee^{1,3}; J.H. Sung^{1,3}; T.M. Jeong^{1,3}; 1 Center for Relativistic Laser Science, Inst. for Basic Science, Korea; 2 Dept of Physics and Photon Science, GIST, Korea; 3 Advanced Photonics Research Inst., GIST, Korea

Wednesday, July 2

11:30-12:00 Code: WeR5-05, Invited

Bulanov Sergei

Laser Ion Acceleration for Hadron Therapy

S. V. Bulanov, Kansai Photon Science Inst., JAEA, Japan

12:00-12:30 Code: WeR5-06, Invited

Bychenkov Valery

Optimized sources of laser-triggered ions from ultra-thin foils

V.Yu.Bychenkov, A.V.Brantov, E.A.Govras; Lebedev Physical Institute RAS Russia

12:30-13:00 Code: WeR5-07, Invited

Kawata Shigeo

Laser Ion Acceleration Control

S. Kawata, T. Nagashima, M. Takano, D. Kamiyama, D. Barada, Y. Y. Ma, *Q. Kong, *P. X. Wang, *Y. J. Gu, *X. Li; Utsunomiya University, Japan; *Fudan University, China

13:00-13:30 Code: WeR5-08, Invited

Korzhimanov Artem

Low- and mid-Z ion acceleration by ultraintense femtosecond lasers in structured targets

A.V.Korzhimanov, E.S.Efimenko, A.V.Kim, S.V.Golubev; Institute of Applied Physics RAS, Russia

Wednesday, July 2

15:00-15:30 Code: WeR5-09, Invited

Murakami Masakatsu

Proton Beam Generation with Nanotube Accelerator

M. Murakami¹, M. Tanaka², T. Kaneko³, T. Kato³, K. Yamanoil; ¹ Inst. of Laser Engineering, Osaka Univ., ² Chubu Univ., Aichi, Tohoku Univ., Japan

15:30-15:45 Code: WeR5-10

Govras Evgeny

Ion Acceleration from Laser-Irradiated Thin Targets

E.A. Govras ^{1,2}, V.Yu. Bychenkov ^{1,2}, A.V. Brantov ^{1,2}; ¹ Lebedev Physics Institute RAS, ² Center for fundamental and applied research, VNIIA, Rosatom, Russia

15:45-16:15 Code: WeR5-11, Invited

Andreev Nikolay

Laser wakefield electron acceleration to multi-GeV energies in guiding structures.

N.E. Andreev, Joint Inst. for High Temperatures of RAS, Russia

16:15-16:45 Code: WeR5-12, Invited

Malka Victor

Compact X ray beams produced with laser plasma accelerators

V. Malka, Lab. d'Optique Applique'e, ENSTA-ParisTech, CNRS, France

16:45-17:00 Code: WeR5-13

Kulagin Victor V.

Generation of Terahertz and Infrared Relativistic Half-Cycle Pulses in Laser Pulse Interaction with Nanodimensional Targets

Victor V. Kulagin ^{1,2}, Vladimir A. Cherepenin ², D. N. Gupta ³; ¹ Sternberg State Astronomical Institute, Lomonosov Moscow State University, ² Institute of Radioengineering and Electronics RAS, ³ Institute of Radioengineering and Electronics RAS, Russia**Wednesday, July 2**

17:30-18:00 Code: WeR5-15, Invited

Andreev Alexander

Generation of X-ray and transport of fast electrons in nano-structured targets irradiated by relativistic intense laser pulses

A.A Andreev^{1,2,3}, K.Yu. Platonov^{1,4}; ¹ Vavilov State Optical Institute, Russia; ² Max Born Institute, Germany; ³ St. Petersburg State University, Russia; ⁴ State Technical University St. Petersburg, Russia

18:00-18:30 Code: WeR5-16, Invited

Tikhonchuk Vladimir

Target charging and electromagnetic field emission in the short pulse laser-plasma experiments

V. T. Tikhonchuk¹, J.-L. Dubois², F. Lubrano-Lavaderci², J. Gazave², D. Raffestin², J. Ribolzi², A. Compant La Fontaine³, E. d'Humières¹, S. Hulin¹, Ph. Nicolaïl, and A. Poyél; ¹ Centre Lasers Intenses & Applications, Univ. Bordeaux, CNRS, CEA, France; ² CEA/DAM/CESTA, France; ³ CEA/DAM/DIF, France

18:30-19:00 Code: WeR5-17, Invited

Fiedorowicz Henryk

Laser plasma sources of soft X-rays and extreme ultraviolet (EUV) for application

H. Fiedorowicz, Inam Ul Ahad, A. Bartnik, T. Fok, R. Jarocki, B. Korczyk, J. Kostecki, A. Szczurek, M. Szczurek, P. Wachulak, L. Wegrzynski; Military University of Technology; Poland

Thursday, July 3

15:00-15:30 Code: ThR5-18, Invited

Charalambidis Dimitrios

Non-linear processes in the XUV: An advanced tool for attosecond pulse metrology and applications

D.Charalambidis; FORTH-IESL and Univ. of Crete, Greece

15:30-15:45 Code: ThR5-19

Serebryannikov Evgeny

Enhancement of optical harmonic generation by free-state electrons in a long wavelength driver field

E.E.Serebryannikov ^{1,2}, A.M.Zheltikov ^{1,2,3}; ¹ Lomonosov Moscow State University, ² Russian Quantum Center, Russia; ³ Texas A&M University, USA

15:45-16:00 Code: ThR5-20

Zemlyanov A.A.Numerical Simulations on Self-focusing and Filamentation of Multi-Terawatt Picosecond CO₂-Laser Pulse in Air

A.A.Zemlyanov, Yu.E.Geints; V.E.Zuev Institute of Atmospheric Optics SB RAS; Russia

16:00-16:15 Code: ThR5-21

Chizhov Pavel

Femtosecond filament plasma channel formation and decay study by transverse optical interferometry.

P. A. Chizhov, V. V. Bukin, S. V. Garnov; General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

16:15-16:30 Code: ThR5-22

Mokrousova Daria

Filamentation of IR and UV double femtosecond laser pulses

A.A. Ionin 1, S.I. Kudryashov 1, D.V. Mokrousova 1,2, L.V. Seleznev 1, D.V. Sinitsyn 1, E.S. Sunchugasheva 1, 2; 1 LPI RAS, 2 MIPT; Russia

16:30-16:45 Code: ThR5-23

Seleznev L

Filamentation of focused femtosecond laser pulse and plasma channel formation in the vicinity of geometric focus

A.A. Ionin 1, D.V. Mokrousova 1,2, L.V. Seleznev 1, A.P. Shustikova 1,2, D.V. Sinitsyn 1, E.S. Sunchugasheva E.S.1,2, A.A. Dergachev 3, V.P.

Kandidov 3, S.A. Shlenov 3; 1 Lebedev Physical Institute RAS, 2 Moscow Institute of Physics and Technology, 3 Lomonosov Moscow State

University; Russia

16:45-17:00 Code: ThR5-24

Sunchugasheva E.S.

Femtosecond laser pulse filamentation with wavefront modulation via pass-through optics

A.A. Ionin 1, D.V. Mokrousova 1,2, L.V. Seleznev 1, A.P. Shustikova 1,2, D.V. Sinitsyn 1, E.S. Sunchugasheva 1,2, A.A. Dergachev 3, V.P. Kandidov 3,

S.A. Shlenov 3; 1 Lebedev Physical Institute RAS, 2 Moscow Institute of Physics and Technology, 3 Moscow State University; Russia

Thursday, July 3

17:30-17:45 Code: ThR5-25

Trunov Vladimir

Dual-Channel Multiterawatt Laser System with Coherent Beam Combining

S. N. Bagayev, V. I. Trunov, E. V. Pestryakov, S. A. Frolov, V. E. Leshchenko, V. A. Vasiliev; Institute of Laser Physics SB RAS, Russia

17:45-18:00 Code: ThR5-26

Bulushev Evgeny

Optical inspection of microchannels formed by femtosecond laser on glass

Victor P. Bessmelsev, Evgeny D. Bulushev, Alexander V. Dostovalov; Institute of Automation and Electrometry SB RAS, Russia

18:00-18:15 Code: ThR5-27

Wang Yanzhi

Reverse and compensation approach of the deposition thickness in manufacturing chirped mirrors

Yanzhi Wang, Kui Yi, Hongji Qi, Guohang Hu, Jianda Shao; Shanghai Institute of Optics and Fine Mechanics; P.R. China

18:15-18:30 Code: ThR5-28

Malevich Vitaly

Spectral dependence of a picosecond anisotropic photoconductivity in cubic semiconductor

Y. Malevich 1, R. Adomavicius 1, A. Krotkus 1, V. Pacebutas 1, V. Malevich 2; 1 Center for Physical Sciences and Technology, Lithuania; 2

Institute of Physics NAS Belarus, Belarus

18:30-18:45 Code: ThR5-29

Kalinichev Aleksei

Nonlinear Doppler-Free Comb-spectroscopy in counter-propagating fields

S.A. Pulkin, A. Kalinichev, V. Arnautov, S.V. Uvarova, S. Savel'eva; St. Petersburg State University, Russia

18:45-19:00 Code: ThR5-30

Ahmadi Tara

Three-level Photon Echo for Quasi-degenerated Levels

T. Ahmadi, S.A. Pulkin, V. Shevtsov; St. Petersburg State University, Russia

19:00-19:15 Code: ThR5-31

Dostovalov Alexandr

Femtosecond point-by-point inscription of fiber Bragg gratings through the polyimide coating

A.V. Dostovalov 1, A.A. Wolf 1, S.A. Babin 1,2; 1 Institute of Automation and Electrometry SB RAS; 2 Novosibirsk State University, Russia

Poster presentations

Thursday, July 3

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR5-p01

Tsybalov Ivan

Relativistic laser driven hot particles generation in undercritical pre-plasma of solid targets

I.N. Tsybalov 1, K.A. Ivanov 1, S.A. Shulyapov 1, P.A. Ksenofontov 1,2, R.V. Volkov 1, A.B. Savel'ev 1, A.V. Brantov 2, V.Yu. Bychenkov 2; 1 Lomonosov Moscow State University, 2 Lebedev Physical Institute RAS; Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR5-p02

Ishino Masahiko

Investigation of interactions of soft x-ray laser pulses with matters

M. Ishino 1, N. Hasegawa 1, M. Nishikino 1, M. Yamagiwa 1, T. Kawachi 1, T. A. Pikuz 2, A. Ya. Faenov 2, and I. Yu. Skobelev 2; 1 Japan Atomic Energy Agency, Japan; 2 Joint Institute for High Temperatures RAS, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR5-p03

Lebo Ivan

On the possibility of neutron yield enhancement in fusion targets at laser energy ~ 1 MJ

I.G. Lebo, A.I. Lebo; Moscow State Technical University (MIREA), Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR5-p04

Brendel Vadim

Laser driven ultra-wideband microwave pulse generator numerical simulation

V. M. Brendel, V.V. Bukin, S.V. Garnov, T.V. Dolmatov, O.T. Loza, S.P. Sadvoskiy, P.A. Chijov, V.P. Tarakanov; General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR5-p05

Oshemkov Sergey

Modification of photomasks substrates by ultrashort laser pulses in modern lithography

Sergey Oshemkov, Vladimir Dmitriev, Erez Graitzer, Guy Ben-Zvi and Vladimir Kruglyakov; Carl Zeiss SMS Ltd., Israel

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR5-p06

Goriaev Andrei

Investigation of hard X-ray generation at oblique incidence of femtosecond laser pulses on the copper foil targets.

A.A. Goriaev 1, A.A. Andreev 1,2, N. Zhavoronkov 2, K.Yu. Platonov 3, M.V. Sedov 1; 1 St. Petersburg State University, Russia; 2 Max-Born-Institut, Germany; 3 St. Petersburg State Polytechnical University, Russia

09:00-13:30 Code: ThR5-p07

Platonov Konstantin

Two-stage ion bunch acceleration in electric field of a foil targets irradiated by intensive laser pulses

A.A. Andreev 1,2, P.Nickles 1, K.Yu. Platonov; 1 Max Born Institute, Germany; 2 St. Petersburg State University, Russia

Session: R6. Nanophotonics and Biophotonics

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Tuesday, July 1

09:30-10:00 Code: TuR6-01, Invited

Blau Werner

Nanocarbon-Based Materials for Non-Linear Optical Applications and Ultrafast Laser Applications

A. A. Murray, J. J. Magan and W. J. Blau; Trinity College Dublin, Ireland

10:00-10:30 Code: TuR6-02, Invited

Noury Adrien

Carbon Nanotubes photonics: towards integrated LASER

A. Noury 1, X. Le Roux 1, E. Gaufrès 2, L. Vivien 1, N. Izard 1; 1 Univ. Paris Sud, France; 2 Université de Montréal, Canada

10:30-11:00 Code: TuR6-03, Invited

Obraztsova Elena

Linear and non-linear optical properties of filled single-wall carbon nanotubes

E.D. Obraztsova 1, A.A. Tonkikh 2, P.V. Fedotov 1, A.S. Alekseev 1, P.A. Obraztsov 1, V.I. Tsebro 2, K. Kaunisto 3, A.G. Nasibulin 4, E.I. Kauppinen 4, A.L.Chuvilin 5; 1 General Physics Institute RAS, 2 Lebedev Physical Institute RAS, Russia; 3 Technical University of Tampere, 4 Aalto University, Finland; 5 CIC nanoGUNE Consolider, Spain

Tuesday, July 1

11:30-12:00 Code: TuR6-05, Invited

Vlasov Andrey

Photo-physical processes in systems containing SWCNT-based hybrids with regard to optical power limiting

Andrey Yu. Vlasov1, Inna M. Belousova2, Ivan M. Kislyakov3; 1 St. Petersburg State University, 2 Vavilov State Optical Institute, 3 National Research University ITMO, Russia

12:00-12:30 Code: TuR6-06, Invited

Katz Eugene A.

Angle restriction of photon emission for ultraefficient photovoltaics: experimental proof of concept

Eugene A. Katz 1, Avi Braun 1, Daniel Feuermann 1, Jeffrey M. Gordon 1, Brendan M. Kayes 2; 1 Department of Solar Energy and Environmental Physics, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Israel; 2 Alta Devices Inc., USA

12:30-13:00 Code: TuR6-07, Invited

Rozhkova Natalia

Hybrid structures of shungite nanocarbon

N.N. Rozhkova, S.S.Rozhkov, A.A. Mikhailina; Institute of Geology Karelian Research Centre RAS, Russia

13:00-13:30 Code: TuR6-08, Invited

Barash Eugene

Practical Limits of Excimer Laser Lithography/ Advanced Optical Technologies in fabrication of 20nm, 14nm and 10nm IC structures using 193nm Excimer Laser Projection Imaging

Eugene Barash 1, R. P. Seisyan 2; 1 GLOBALFOUNDRIES, USA, 2 Ioffe Physical Technical Institute, Russia

Tuesday, July 1

15:00-15:15 Code: TuR6-09

Venediktova Anastasia

Scaling reciprocal of nanotubes aggregation degree in aqueous suspensions against nonlinear optical properties of the systems

Anastasia Venediktova 1, Elena Obraztsova 2, Dmitry Videnichev 3, Eugene Katz 4; 1 St. Petersburg State University, 2 General Physics Institute RAS, 3 Vavilov State Optical Institute, Russia; 4 Ben Gurion University of the Negev, Israel

15:15-15:30 Code: TuR6-10

Yelleswarapu Chandra

Nonlinear optical properties of pyrrolic organic dyes

Maryam Hatamimoslehabadi, Chandra S. Yelleswarapu, Mathieu Frenette, and Jonathan Rochford; University of Massachusetts Boston, USA

15:30-15:45 Code: TuR6-11

Ryzhov Anton

Nonlinear multilayer Fabry-Perot resonators as narrowband optical limiters

A. A. Ryzhov, I. M. Belousova, G. A. Muranova; Vavilov State Optical Institute, Russia

15:45-16:00 Code: TuR6-12

Ushakova Elena

Self-assembled PbS QDs of different size

E.V. Ushakova 1, V.V. Golubkov 2, A.P. Litvin 1, P.S. Parfenov 1, S.A. Cherevko 1, A.V. Fedorov 1, A.V. Baranov 1; 1 National Research University ITMO; 2 Institute of Silicate Chemistry RAS, Russia

16:00-16:15 Code: TuR6-13

Agruzov Petr

Magneto-optic effects in microstructured fiber with ferrofluid cladding in the pulsed mode

Petr M. Agruzov 1, Ivan V. Pleshakov 1, Efim E. Bibik 2, Alexander V. Shamray 1; 1 Ioffe Physical Technical Institute RAS, 2 St. Petersburg State Institute of Technology, Russia

16:15-16:30 Code: TuR6-14

Kucherik Alexey

Laser formation of colloidal alloys of the noble nanoparticles and deposition of the microclusters on the glass substrate

A. Kucherik 1, A. Antipov, 1, S. Arakelian 1, S. Kutrovskaya 1, K. Khorkov 1, A. Povolotckaia 2, A. Povolotskiy 2, A. Manshina 2; 1. Stoletov's Vladimir State University, 2 St. Petersburg State University, Russia

16:30-16:45 Code: TuR6-15

Kopylov Denis

Studies of short pulse propagation in 1D porous silicon based photonic crystals with spatially modulated photonic band gap

D.A. Kopylov, E.A. Mamonov, S.E. Svyakhovskiy, A.I. Maydykovsky; Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia

16:45-17:00 Code: TuR6-16

Perminov Sergey

Rayleigh-Wood's Resonances in the Near-Field Scattering by Periodic Array of Nanowires

L.L. Frumin 1,2, A.V. Nemykin 1,2, D.A. Shapiro 1,2, S.V. Perminov 3; 1 Institute of Automation and Electrometry SB RAS, 2 Novosibirsk State University, 3 A.V. Rzhanov Institute of Semiconductor Physics SB RAS, Russia

Tuesday, July 1

17:30-18:00 Code: TuR6-17, Invited

Vartanyan Tigran

Optics of thin composite films: plasmon enhanced resonance response or coupling induced shift of the plasmon band?

T.A. Vartanyan, A.O. Orlova; National Research University ITMO, Russia

18:00-18:15 Code: TuR6-18

Kudryashov Sergey

Spectral mapping, tracking and utilizing

Sergey Kudryashov, Pavel Danilov, Andrey Ionin, Sergey Makarov, Pavel Saltuganov, Leonid Seleznev, Elena Sunchugasheva, Vladislav Yurovskikh, Dmitry Zayarny; Lebedev Physical Institute RAS, Russia

18:15-18:30 Code: TuR6-19

Guo Guang Yu

Optical Multiple Bistability in Metal-Insulator-Metal Plasmonic Waveguides Side-coupled with Twin Resonators

Ruei-Cheng Shiu,1,2 Yung-Chiang Lan2 and Guang-Yu Guo1; 1 National Taiwan University, Department of Physics, 2 Department of Physics, National Cheng Kung University

18:30-18:45 Code: TuR6-20

Makarov Sergey

Parabolic-like nanoantennas fabrication by femtosecond laser pulses for strong-field plasmonics

M. A. Gubkol, A. A. Ionin1, S. I. Kudryashov1, S. V. Makarov1, A. A. Rudenkol, L. V. Seleznev1, D. V. Sinitzyn1, I.V. Treshin1, W. Husinsky2, C.S.R. Nathala2; 1 Lebedev Physical Institute RAS, Russia; 2 Vienna University of Technology, Austria

Wednesday, July 2

09:00-09:30 Code: WeR6-22, Invited

Hanley Cormac

Quantum Dots and Quantum Dot Based Polymer Composites

Cormac Hanley, Yurii K. Gun'ko; Trinity College Dublin, Ireland

09:30-10:00 Code: WeR6-23, Invited

Wang Jun

Nonlinear absorption and nonlinear refraction of two-dimensional transition metal dichalcogenides

Jun Wang ; Key Laboratory of Materials for High-Power Laser, Shanghai Institute of Optics and Fine Mechanics, Chinese Academy of Sciences; P.R. China

10:00-10:15 Code: WeR6-24

Kryzhanovskaya Natalia

Influence of active region and resonator design on characteristics of microdisk lasers.

N.V. Kryzhanovskaya1, M.V. Maximov1, A.M. Nadtochiy1, A.E. Zhukov1, E.I. Moiseev1, I.I. Shostak1, A.V. Savel'ev1, A.A. Lipovskii1, D.V. Karpov1, M.M. Kulagina2, Vashanova K.A.2, J. Laukkanen3, J. Tommila 4; 1 St Petersburg Academic University, Russia; 2 Ioffe Physical-Technical Institute, Russia; 3 University of Eastern Finland, 4 Tampere University of Technology, Finland;

10:15-10:30 Code: WeR6-25

Parfenov Petr

Luminescence and Morphology Study of PbS Quantum Dots in Porous Matrix

P.S. Parfenov, A.P. Litvin, E.V. Ushakova, A.V. Fedorov, A.V. Baranov; National Research University ITMO, Russia

10:30-10:45 Code: WeR6-26

Makarov Nikolay S.

Ultrafast Spectroscopy of CuInSeS Colloidal Quantum Dots: Auger Recombination, Carrier Multiplication, and Electron Transfer

Nikolay S. Makarov, Hunter McDaniel, Istvan Robel, Victor I. Klimov; Center for Advanced Solar Photophysics, Chemistry Division, Los Alamos National Laboratory, USA

10:45-11:00 Code: WeR6-27

Makarov Nikolay S.

Efficient Auger-Assisted Up-Conversion in Engineered PbSe/CdSe Core/Shell Colloidal Quantum Dots

Nikolay S. Makarov, Qianglu Lin, Kirill Velizhanin, Victor I. Klimov; Center for Advanced Solar Photophysics, Chemistry Division, Los Alamos National Laboratory, USA

Wednesday, July 2

11:30-12:00 Code: WeR6-28, Invited

Fainberg B.D.

Coherent laser control of current via molecular nanojunctions with semiconductor and graphene contacts

B.D. Fainberg; Holon Institute of Technology; Israel

12:00-12:30 Code: WeR6-29, Invited

Nikonorov Nikolay

Development of New Photonic and Plasmonic Devices Based on Nanostructured Glasses and Glassceramics

N.V. Nikonorov; National Research University ITMO, Russia

12:30-13:00 Code: WeR6-30, Invited

Smirnov Vadim

Advanced Narrow Band Filters in PTR Glass for Raman Spectroscopy

Vadim Smirnov, Oleksiy Mokhun, Valery Koulechov, Alexei Glebov and Leonid Glebov; OptiGrate Corp, USA

13:00-13:15 Code: WeR6-31

Skoptsov Nikolai

Luminescence of Erbium Ions in Transparent Glass-Ceramics Containing (Er,Yb)NbO₄ Nanocrystals

N.A. Skoptsov¹, K.V. Yumashev¹, O.S. Dymshits², A.A. Zhilin², I.P. Alekseeva²; ¹ Belarusian National Technical University, Belarus; ² Vavilov State Optical Institute, Russia

13:15-13:30 Code: WeR6-32

Alekseev Prokhor

New scanning probe microscopy near-field imaging method for laser radiation intensity mapping

P.A. Alekseev¹, M.S. Dunaevskiy¹, A.M. Monahov¹, A.N. Titkov¹, A.N. Baranov², P. Girard², R. Teissier²; ¹ Ioffe Physical Technical Institute RAS, Russia; ² Institut d'Electronique du Sud UM2-CNRS Montpellier, France

Thursday, July 3

09:00-09:30 Code: Thr6-33, Invited

Rao Devulapalli

Nonlinear optics of some nontoxic nanomaterials

D. V. G. L. N. Rao; Chandra S. Yelleswarapu; University of Massachusetts Boston, USA

09:30-10:00 Code: Thr6-34, Invited

Krasnovsky Alexander

Laser photochemistry of oxygen: application to studies of oxygen photonics.

A.A. Krasnovsky; A.N. Bach Institute of Biochemistry, Russia

10:00-10:30 Code: Thr6-35, Invited

Ferrini Gabriele

A multimodal approach to time-resolved optical spectroscopy for biomolecular detection

F. Banfi, C. Giannetti, G. Ferrini; Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Italy;

10:30-10:45 Code: Thr6-36

Asimov M.M.

The Phenomenon of Laser-Induced Oxyhemoglobin Photodissociation and its Biomedical Application

M.M. Asimov¹, R.M. Asimov², D.B. Vladimirov¹, A.N. Rubinov¹; ¹ Institute of Physics NAS Belarus, ² Sensotronica Ltd.; Belarus; Institute of Physics NAS Belarus

10:45-11:00 Code: Thr6-37

Dolgushin Sergey

Particular Features of Time-Dependent Diffusion Models Applied in Optical Methods for Medical Diagnostics

S.A. Dolgushin ¹, S.A. Titenok ¹, S.A. Tereshchenko ¹, Jorge Bouza Domínguez ²; ¹ National Research University of Electronic Technology, Russia; ² Bishop's University, Canada

Thursday, July 3

11:30-11:45 Code: Thr6-38

Asimov R.M.

Biomedical Application of Laser-Induced Muscle Oxyhemoglobin Photodissociation

M.M. Asimov, R.M. Asimov¹, A.N. Rubinov; Institute of Physics NAS Belarus, ¹ Sensotronica Ltd., Belarus; Institute of Physics NAS Belarus

11:45-12:00 Code: Thr6-39

Jeon Min Yong

Fiber-optic Electric field sensor based on wavelength-swept laser

Myeong Ock Ko ¹, Sung-Jo Kim ¹, Jong-Hyun Kim ¹, and Min Yong Jeon ¹, Bong Wan Lee ²; ¹ Chungnam National University, ² FiberPro Inc.; Rep. of Korea

12:00-12:15 Code: Thr6-40

Slabko Vitaliy

Self-organized aggregation simulation of resonant nanoparticles in a laser field

V.V. Slabko ¹, A.S. Tsipotan ¹, M.A. Gerasimova ¹, A.S. Aleksandrovsky ^{1,2}; ¹ Siberian Federal University, Russia; ² L.V. Kirensky Institute of Physics, SB RAS, Russia

12:15-12:30 Code: Thr6-41

Pukhov Konstantin

The spontaneous emission rate of emitter outside and inside of the core-shell nanoparticle

K.K. Pukhov ¹, S.K. Sekatskii ²; ¹ General Physics Institute RAS, Russia; ² Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), Switzerland

12:30-12:45 Code: ThR6-42

Dunina Elena

Influence of configuration interaction on absorption transition intensities of rare-earth ions in laser materials

Elena Dunina 1, Alexei Kornienko 1, Liudmila Fomicheva 2; 1 Vitebsk State Technological University, 2 Belarusian State University of Informatics and Radioelectronics, Belarus

Poster presentations

Wednesday, July 2

15:00-19:30 Code: WeR6-p02

Kornienko Alexey

Definition of covalence parameters in trigonal systems on optical spectrum

Alexei Kornienko 1, Elena Dunina 1, Liudmila Fomicheva 2; 1 Vitebsk State Technological University, 2 Belarusian State University of Informatics and Radioelectronics, Belarus

15:00-19:30 Code: WeR6-p03

Avetissov Igor

Hybrid nanofilms with laser-control luminescence

Rasim Saifutyarov, Andrew Khomyakov, Alina Akkuzina, Roman Avetisov, Olga Petrova, Igor Avetissov; D. Mendeleev University of Chemical Technology of Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: WeR6-p04

Avetissov Igor

Spectral properties of CdTe-CdSe powders with controlled nonstoichiometry

Andrew Khomyakov, Elena Mozhevitina, Vladimir Kuzmin, Nataljia Konjkova, Igor Avetissov; D. Mendeleev University of Chemical Technology of Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: WeR6-p05

Plastun Alexander

Effect of micro deformation on photonic bandgap fibre transmission

Alexander Plastun, Andrey Konukhov; Saratov State University; Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: WeR6-p06

Petrova Olga

Transparent glass-ceramics doped with Nd³⁺ or Er³⁺ based on lead-barium fluoroborate

O.B. Petrova, T.S. Sevostjanova, M.O. Anurova, A.V. Khomyakov; D. Mendeleev University of Chemical Technology of Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: WeR6-p07

Stepanova Irina

Bismuth-germanium oxide glasses and glass-ceramics doped with Nd³⁺ or Yb³⁺

I.V. Stepanova, A.V. Khomyakov, K.G. Gavrish; D. Mendeleev University of Chemical Technology of Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: WeR6-p08

Subbotin Kirill

Transparent Cr:LiGaSiO₄ nano-glass-ceramics as the promising laser material

Kirill A. Subbotin, Valerii V. Voronov, Dmitrii A. Nikolaev, Evgenii V.Zharikov; General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: WeR6-p09

Kuraptsev Alexey

Microscopic approach to calculation of the spontaneous decay of an excited atom located near an atomic cluster

A.S. Kuraptsev, I.M. Sokolov; Saint Petersburg State Polytechnic University; Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: WeR6-p10

Chekmasov Sergey

LASER DIAGNOSTICS OF DISPERSIVE SYSTEMS WITH SUPERCRITICAL COMPONENT

Sergey Chekmasov, Dmitry Zimnyakov; Saratov State Technical University; Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: WeR6-p11

Leonov Mikhail

Transient photoluminescence from semiconductor nanodumbbells

M.Yu. Leonov 1, I.D. Rukhlenko 1,2, A.S. Baimuratov 1, A.V. Baranov 1, A.V. Fedorov 1; 1 National Research University ITMO, Russia; 2 Monash University, Australia

15:00-19:30 Code: WeR6-p12

Plastun Inna

Nonlinear optical properties of open-ended armchair single-wall carbon nanotubes (SW-CNT)

Inna L. Plastun, Dmitry A. Zimnyakov, Andrey N. Bokarev, Sergey A. Yuvchenko; Gagarin State Technical University, Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: WeR6-p13

Baimuratov Anvar

Phonon-induced photoluminescence from a single quantum dot in the regime vibrational resonance

Anvar S. Baimuratov 1, Vadim K. Turkov 1, Mikhail Yu. Leonov 1, Yurii K. Gun'ko 1, Alexander V. Baranov 1, Anatoly V. Fedorov 1, Ivan D. Rukhlenko 2, 1 National Research University ITMO, Russia; 2 Monash University, Australia

15:00-19:30 Code: WeR6-p14

Pishchalnikov Roman

Numerical studies of the photosynthetic reaction center femtosecond transient absorption

R.Y. Pishchalnikov, S.M. Pershin; General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: WeR6-p15

Bokarev Andrey

Investigation of open-ended armchair single-wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNT) properties by numerical simulations

Andrey N. Bokarev, Inna L. Plastun; Gagarin State Technical University of Saratov, Russia.

15:00-19:30 Code: WeR6-p16

Mayakova Mariya

Synthesis and study of barium fluoride powder doped with scandium as scintillation ceramics charge

M. N. Mayakova 1, P. P. Fedorov1, S. V. Kuznetsov1, V. V. Voronov1, A. E. Baranchikov2, P.A. Rodnyi 3; 1 General Physics Institute RAS, 2 Kurnakov Institute of General and Inorganic Chemistry RAS, 3 St. Petersburg State Polytechnical University; Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: WeR6-p17

Kislyakov Ivan

Free-base and metallated bis-tetraphenylporphyrin covalent ensembles for optical power limiting

Ivan M. Kislyakov1, Inna M. Belousova1, Svyatoslav A. Povarov1, Ivan S. Sheiko1, Alexander S. Konev2, Daniil A. Lukyanov2, Alexander F. Khlebnikov2; 1 National Research University ITMO, 2 St. Petersburg State University; Russia

Session: R7. Lasers in Environmental Monitoring

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Wednesday, July 2

15:00-15:30 Code: WeR7-01, Invited

Bunkin Alexey

Remote sensing of seawater and drifting ice by compact Raman lidar

A.F.Bunkin, Prokhorov General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

15:30-15:45 Code: WeR7-02

Utkin Andrei B.

LIF LIDAR for in situ, in vivo assessment of algal communities and higher plants

Andrei B. Utkin 1, Paulo Cartaxana 2 and Carla Gameiro 2; 1 Technical University of Lisbon, 2 Centro de Oceanografia, Faculty of Sciences of Lisbon University; Portugal

15:45-16:00 Code: WeR7-03

Utkin Andrei B.

Mapping of Algal Communities in Tagus Estuary Using Mobile LIF LIDAR Sensor

Carla Gameiro 1, Paulo Cartaxana 1 and Andrei B. Utkin 2; 1 Centro de Oceanografia, Faculty of Sciences of Lisbon University, INOV - INESC Inovação and ICEMS IST, Technical University of Lisbon, Portugal

16:00-16:30 Code: WeR7-04, Invited

Petrov Nikolay

Design and development of underwater laser spectroscopic system for hydrocarbon deposits exploration

V.G. Bespalov 1, E.A. Makarov 1., A.P. Zhevlakov 2, Yu.I. Soldatov 2, 1 National Research University ITMO; 2 Vavilov State Optical Institute, Russia

16:30-16:45 Code: WeR7-05

Goryainov Viktor

Oceanological Monitoring of Fishing Areas using Lidars

V. I. Chernook1, A. N. Vasilyev1, Yu. A. Goldin2, B. A. Gureev2, V. S. Goryainov3, A. A. Buznikov3; 1 JSC "Giprorybflot", 2 Institute of Oceanology RAS, 3 St. Petersburg Electrotechnical University "LETI"; Russia

16:45-17:00 Code: WeR7-06

Grishkanich Aleksandr

Monitoring of methane emissions in the Arctic by laser sensing to assess climate change

A.S. Grishkanich 1,2, A.A. Buznikov 1, V.V. Elizarov 1, S.V. Kascheev 2, A.P. Zhevlakov 2 ; 1 St. Petersburg Electrotechnical University

"LETI", 2 National Research University ITMO, Russia

Wednesday, July 2

17:30-18:00 Code: WeR7-07, Invited

Pershin Sergey

Multilayered clouds monitoring during blizzard by eye-safe Lidar-prototype for NASA mission "Mars Polar Lander-99"

S.M. Pershin; General Physics Institute RAS; Russia

18:00-18:15 Code: WeR7-08

Pershin S.M.

Trouble free eye-safe lidar based on pulsed diode laser& quantum counter for environmental monitoring

S.M. Pershin1, V.N. Lednev1, V.S. Makarov2, A.V. Turin2; 1 Prokhorov General Physics Institute RAS, 2 Space Research Institute RAS; Russia

18:15-18:30 Code: WeR7-09

Pisani Marco

Synthetic wavelength interferometer for absolute distance measurements on Earth and in space

M. Astrua, M. Pisani, M. Zucco; INRIM, Italy

18:30-19:00 Code: WeR7-10, Invited

Beloborodov Vitaly

Problems of Perfecting and Metrological Assurance of Laser Gas Analyzers

Leonid Konopelko, Vitaly Beloborodov, Dmitry Rumiantsev, Yan Chubchenko; D.I.Mendeleyev Metrology Institute (VNIIM); Russia

19:00-19:15 Code: WeR7-11

Grishkanich Aleksandr

Laser sensor for airborne prospecting method of oil & gas deposits

A.S. Grishkanich 1,2, V.G. Bepalov 2, S.A. Bogoslovsky 3, V.V. Elizarov 2, A.A. Il'inskiy 3, S.V. Kascheev 2, E.A. Makarov 2, A.P. Zhevlakov 2; 1 St Petersburg Electrotechnical University "LETI", 2 National Research University ITMO, 3 All Russia Petroleum Research Exploration Institute, Russia

19:15-19:30 Code: WeR7-12

Grishkanich Aleksandr

Laser sensor for radiation monitoring

A.S. Grishkanich 1,2, A.A. Buznikov 1, V.V. Elizarov 1, S.K. Vasiliev 3, S.V. Kascheev 2, A.P. Zhevlakov 2 ; 1 St. Petersburg Electrotechnical University "LETI", 2 National Research University ITMO, 3 Emergency Technical Center Rosatom, Russia

Thursday, July 3

15:00-15:30 Code: Thr7-13, Invited

Kozliner Marat

Application THz-Raman Spectroscopy for identification of chemical, and biological products

Egor Iasenkol, Vladimir Chelibanov1, Alexander Marugin2, Marat Kozliner3; 1 National Research University ITMO, 2 JSC OPTEC Ltd., Russia; 3 JSC OPTEC Ltd., USA

15:30-15:45 Code: Thr7-14

Lassen Mikael

Compact Sensor for Photoacoustic Monitoring and Photochemical Dissociation of NO2

Mikael Lassen, Anders Brusck, David Balslev-Clausen and Jan C.Petersen ; Danish Fundamental Metrology; Denmark

15:45-16:15 Code: Thr7-15, Invited

Shemanin Valery G.

Laser sensing of aerosol flows

Valery G. Shemanin ; Novorossiysk Polytech Ins KubSTU; Russia

16:15-16:30 Code: Thr7-16

Suvorina Anastasia

Profiling of the forest fire aerosol plume with multiwavelength Raman lidar

A.S. Suvorina 1, I.A. Veselovskii 1, D.N. Whiteman 2, M.Yu. Korenskiy 1; 1 General Physics Institute RAS, Russia; 2 NASA Goddard Space Flight Center, USA;

16:30-16:45 Code: Thr7-17

Turtaev Sergey

Acoustic Sensitivity of the Negative Curvature Hollow Core Fiber

S.N. Turtaev M.I. Belovolov A.E. Levchenko A. F. Kosolapov, A. D. Pryamikov, A.N. Kolyadin; Fiber Optics Research Center RAS, Russia

16:45-17:00 Code: Thr7-18

Kascheev Sergei

UPGRADED RAMAN LIDAR WITH ULTRASPECTRAL RESOLUTION

S.V. Kascheev 1, V.V. Elizarov 1, A.S. Grishkanich 1,2, D.V. Kosachev 4, S.B. Petrov 1,3, A.P. Zhevlakov1,3; 1 National Research University ITMO, 2 St Petersburg Electrotechnical University "LETI", 3 Lasers and Optical Systems, JSC, 4 Gazprom-Transgaz-Ugorsk; Russia

Thursday, July 3

17:30-18:00 Code: Thr7-19, Invited

Nadezhdinskii Alexander

Analytical Applications of Tunable Diode Laser Spectroscopy
A. Nadezhdinskii; General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

18:00-18:15 Code: Thr7-20

Kamenev Wladimir

Combining PIV and PDV Methods for Investigation of Dispersion Media Parameters
V.G. Kamenev, O.N. Koltovoy, K.V. Bandurkin, V.P. Andrianov; Research Institute of Automatics, Russia

18:15-18:45 Code: Thr7-21, Invited

Janssen Christof

High resolution laser absorption spectroscopy in the 10 micron window - from the lab to the atmosphere

C. Janssen 1, H. Elandaloussi 1, Y. Té 1, P. Jeseck 1, C. Boursier 1, C. Rouillé 1, P. Marie-Jeanne 1, X. Zeng 2, H. Willner 2; 1 Sorbonne Universités, Univ Paris 6 / CNRS / Observatoire de Paris / IPSL, France; 2 FB C - Anorganische Chemie, Germany

18:45-19:00 Code: Thr7-22

Rinkevichyus Bronyus

Principles and Applications of Laser Refractography

B.S. Rinkevichyus, I.L.Raskovskaya, A.V.Tolkachev; National research university «MPEI», Russia

19:00-19:15 Code: Thr7-23

Brazhnikov Pavel

Laser Interferometer System for Recording Variations of Light Wavelength

P. Brazhnikov, V. Andrianov, O. Koltovoy, A. Tikhov; Research Institute of Automatics named after N.L. Dukhov, Russia

19:15-19:30 Code: Thr7-24

Elizarov Valentin

Features processing lidar signals in the GHz frequency range

V.V. Elizarov, A.S. Grishkanich, S.V. Kascheev, A.P. Zhevlakov, National Research University ITMO, Russia

Poster presentations

There are no poster presentations in this session.

Session: R8. Nonlinear Photonics: Fundamentals and Applications

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Tuesday, July 1

09:00-09:30 Code: TuR8-01, Invited

Blow Keith

Optical Parametric Amplifiers for Communications

K.J. Blow; Aston University, UK

09:30-09:45 Code: TuR8-02

Agruzov Petr

Nonstationary coherent optical effects in acetylene-filled hollow core photonic crystal fibers

M. Ocegueda 1, E. Hernandez 1, P. Agruzov 2, A. Shamray 2, S. Stepanov 1; 1 CICESE, Mexico; 2 Ioffe Physical Technical Institute RAS, Russia

09:45-10:00 Code: TuR8-04

Fotiadi Andrei

Cooperative Rayleigh-Brillouin scattering in long optical fibers

Andrei A. Fotiadi 1, Ivan Lobach 2, Patrice Mégret 1; 1 University of Mons, Belgium; 2 Institute of Automation and Electrometry SB RAS, Russia

10:00-10:15 Code: TuR8-05

Nyushkov Boris

Thermal enhancement of optical harmonic generation in a fiber-coupled nematic liquid crystal

S.I. Trashkeev 1, B.N. Nyushkov 1,2; 1 Institute of Laser Physics SB RAS, 2 Novosibirsk State University; Russia

10:15-10:30 Code: TuR8-06

Sukhanov Sergey

Effect of SBS on the dynamics of ring fiber laser

L.A.Melnikov, S.V.Sukhanov ; Department of Instrumentation Engineering, Yuri Gagarin State Technical University of Saratov; Russia

10:30-10:45 Code: TuR8-07

Sergeyev Sergey

Vector Solitons with Fast and Slowly Evolving States of Polarization in Mode Locked Fiber Lasers

S. V. Sergeyev 1, T. Habruseva 1, V. Tsaturian 1, Ch. Mou 1, G. Jacobsen 2, S. Popov 3, S. K. Turitsyn 3; 1 AIPT, Aston University, UK; 2 Acreo, Sweden; 3 KTH, Sweden

10:45-11:00 Code: TuR8-09

Dukhovnikova N.Yu.

HgGa2S4 optical parametric oscillator

N.Yu. Dukhovnikoval,2, A.A. Boykol, K.G. Zenovl, D.B. Kolkerl, I.V. Sherstovl, I.B. Miroshnichenkol, M.K. Starikoval, A.A. Karapuzikovl, A.I. Karapuzikovl, Yu.V. Kistenyov3, D.A.Kuzmin3; 1 Special Technology, LTD, 2 Novosibirsk state technical university, 3 Siberian state medical university; Russia

Tuesday, July 1

11:30-12:00 Code: TuR8-08, Invited

Schiek Roland

Self-phase modulation in lithium niobate waveguides

Roland Schiek; OTH Regensburg, Germany

12:00-12:15 Code: TuR8-10

Lukanin Vladimir

Two-photon interband absorption coefficients in tungstate and molybdate crystals

V.I. Lukanin, A.Ya. Karasik; General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

12:15-12:30 Code: TuR8-11

Regelskis Kestutis

Peculiarities of second harmonics generation with linearly varying wave-number mismatch along a nonlinear crystal

K. Regelskis, J. Želudevicius, V. Žvirblyte; Center for Physical Sciences & Technology (CPST), Lithuania

12:30-12:45 Code: TuR8-12

Pyragaite Viktorija

Narrowing of angular spectrum of second harmonic beam generated from incoherent conical pump

Viktorija Pyragaite, Paulius Stanislovaitis, Andrius Narmonatas, Valerijus Smilgevičius; Department of Quantum Electronics, Vilnius University; Lithuania

12:45-13:00 Code: TuR8-13

Savelyev Mikhail

Investigation of limiting properties of nonlinear materials

M.S. Savelyev, A.Yu. Gerasimenko, S.A. Tereshchenko, V.M. Podgaetsky; National Research University of Electronic Technology (MIET); Russia

13:00-13:15 Code: TuR8-14

Klimachev Yury

CO AND CO2 LASER RADIATION FREQUENCY CONVERSION IN GaSe AND ZGP: BROADBAND LASER SOURCE EMITTING WITHIN 2.5 - 13.1 MICRONS

A.A. Ionin 1, I.O. Kinyaevskiy 1, Yu.M. Klimachev 1, A.A. Kotkov 1, A.Yu. Kozlov 1, Yu.M. Andreev 2, 1 P.N. Lebedev Physical Institute RAS, 2 Institute of Monitoring of Climatic and Ecological Systems SB RAS, Russia

13:15-13:30 Code: TuR8-15

Kuznetsova Svetlana

Magnetic response of thick dielectric rings

S.M. Kuznetsova, A.V. Maslov, M.I. Bakunov; University of Nizhny Novgorod; Russia

Wednesday, July 2

09:00-09:30 Code: WeR8-16, Invited

Motzkus Marcus

Quantum Control Spectroscopy: Nonlinear (micro) spectroscopy with tailored pulses

Alexander Wipfler, Lukas Brückner, Jean Rehbinder, Tiago Buckup, and Marcus Motzkus; Ruprecht-Karls-Universität Heidelberg, Germany

09:30-10:00 Code: WeR8-17, Invited

Sukhorukov Andrey

Generation of entangled photon pairs on a nonlinear chip

James G. Titchener, Che Wen Wu, Alexander S. Solntsev, Dragomir N. Neshev, and Andrey A. Sukhorukov; Australian National University; Australia

10:00-10:15 Code: WeR8-18

Solntsev Alexander

Biphoton generation and pump filtering in nonlinear adiabatic waveguiding structures

Che Wen Wu, Alexander S. Solntsev, Dragomir N. Neshev, and Andrey. A. Sukhorukov ; Australian National University

10:15-10:45 Code: WeR8-19, Invited

Welch George R.

Time-Resolved Surface-Enhanced Coherent Sensing of Nanoscale Molecular Complexes

George R. Welch, Dmitri V. Voronine, Alexander M. Sinyukov, Xia Hua, Kai Wang, Pankaj K. Jha, Elango Munusamy, Steven E. Wheeler, Alexei V. Sokolov, Marlan O. Scully; Texas A&M University; USA

10:45-11:00 Code: WeR8-20

Veretenov Nikolay

Modulational Instability, Switching Waves, Bistability and Dissipative Solitons at Resonance Excitation of Molecular J-aggregates

N.A. Veretenov 1,2, L.A. Nesterov 1,2, N.N. Rosanov 1,2,3, A.N. Shatsev 1, S.V. Fedorov 1,2; 1 Vavilov State Optical Institute, 2 National Research University ITMO, 3 Ioffe Physical Technical Institute; Russia.

Wednesday, July 2

11:30-12:00 Code: WeR8-21, Invited

Melnikov L.A.

Spontaneous and Stimulated Transitions in the Atoms Embedded into Hyperbolic Metamaterials

L.A.Melnikov 1, M.V.Ryabinina 1, I.S.Nefedov 2; 1 Yuri Gagarin State Technical University of Saratov, Russia; 2 Aalto University, Finland

12:00-12:15 Code: WeR8-22

Akulshin Alexander

Polychromatic directional emission in Rb vapour for remote sensing

Alexander Akulshin1, Dmitry Budker2,3, Eugeny Mikhailov3, Irina Novikova3, and Russell McLean1 ; 1 Swinburne University of Technology, Australia; 2 University of California,, USA; 3 Johannes Gutenberg University, Germany; 4 College of William & MaryWilliamsburg, USA

12:15-12:30 Code: WeR8-23

Tretiak Oleg

Raman spectroscopy investigation of alkene-based anti-relaxation coating

O.Yu. Tretiak, M.V. Balabas, P.K. Olshin; St. Petersburg State University, Russia

12:30-13:00 Code: WeR8-24, Invited

Fratalocchi Andrea

When disorder is just right: on complexity-driven photonics

A. Fratalocchi; KAUST University, Saudi Arabia

13:00-13:30 Code: WeR8-25, Invited

Popov Alexander K.

Mimicking Frequency-mixing in Nonlinear Optical Negative-index Metamaterials: Unidirectional Raman Amplification and Shaping of Optical Pulses

A. K. Popov 1,2, V. V. Slabko 3, S. A. Myslivets 2, M. I. Shalaev 3; 1 Purdue University, 2 University of Wisconsin-Stevens Point, USA; 2 Siberian Federal University, 3 Institute of Physics SB RAS, Russia

Wednesday, July 2

15:00-15:30 Code: WeR8-26, Invited

Maimistov Andrei

The positive-negative index coupled waveguides systems: couplers, arrays and bundles

Andrey I. Maimistov 1,2, Elena V. Kazantseva 2, Ildar R. Gabitov 3,4; 1 Moscow Institute of Physics and Technology, 2 National Nuclear Research University, Russia; 3 University of Arizona, USA; 4 L.D. Landau Institute for Theoretical Physics, Russia

15:30-16:00 Code: WeR8-27, Invited

Desyatnikov Anton

Dynamics of structured light in singular photonic lattices

A. Desyatnikov; Australian National University, Australia

16:00-16:15 Code: WeR8-28

Arkhipov Rostislav

Theoretical Study of Transient Cherenkov Radiation from Periodic Resonance Medium Excited at the Superluminal Velocity

R.M. Arkhipov1, I.Babaushkin2, Yu.A. Tolmachev3, M.V. Arkhipov3; 1 Weierstrass Institute, Germany; 2 Institute of Mathematics, Humboldt University of Berlin, Germany; 3 St. Petersburg State University, Russia

16:15-16:30 Code: WeR8-29

Umemura Nobuhiro

High-accuracy Sellmeier equations for LiInS2 and its applications to the nonlinear optics in LiIn(SxSe1-x)2

K. Kato 1, N. Umemura 1, K. Miyata 2; 1 Chitose Institute of Science and Technology, 2 MegaOpt, Co. Ltd.; Japan

17:00-17:30 Code: WeR8-30, Invited

Sumetsky M.

Surface Nanoscale Axial Photonics (SNAP) Devices

M. Sumetsky, Aston Inst. of Photonics Technologies, Aston Univ., UK; Aston Inst. of Photonics Technologies, Aston Univ., UK

Wednesday, July 2

17:30-18:00 Code: WeR8-32, Invited

Vinogradov Alexey

PT-symmetric systems in optics

A.P. Vinogradov^{1,2,3}, A.A. Zyablovskiy^{1,2}, A.A. Pukhov^{1,2,3}, A.V. Dorofeenko^{1,2,3}, A.A. Lisyansky⁴; 1 FSUE All-Russia Research Institute of Automatics, 2 Moscow Institute of Physics and Technology (State University), 3 Institute for Theoretical and Applied Electromagnetics RAS (ITAE RAS), Russia; 4 Queens College of the City, University of New York, USA

18:00-18:30 Code: WeR8-33, Invited

Tlidi Mustapha

Dynamics of localized structures in broad area semiconductor cavities

M. Tlidi, Univ. Libre de Bruxelles, Belgium; Univ. Libre de Bruxelles

18:30-18:45 Code: WeR8-34

Rosanov Nikolay

Fermi-Ulam Problem for Classical and Quantum Particles in Dynamical Traps

N.N. Rosanov, G.B. Sochilin, V.D. Vinokurova, N.V. Vyssotina; Vavilov State Optical Institute, Russia

18:45-19:00 Code: WeR8-35

Rosanov Nikolay

Fermi-Ulam Problem for Solitons in Dynamical Cavities

N.N. Rosanov, N.V. Vyssotina; Vavilov State Optical Institute, Russia

Thursday, July 3

11:30-12:00 Code: ThR8-36, Invited

Otsuji Taiichi

Graphene Plasmonic Heterostructures for Terahertz Device Applications

T. Otsuji¹, A. Satou¹, S. Boubanga Tombet¹, V. Ryzhii¹, V.V. Popov², M.S. Shur³; 1 Tohoku University, Japan; 2 Kotelnikov Institute of Radio Engineering and Electronics, Russia; 3 Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute, USA

12:00-12:15 Code: ThR8-37

Kozina Olga

Light propagation characteristics of hyperbolic graphene-semiconductor multilayered medium

L. Melnikov¹, O.Kozina², I. Nefedov³; 1 Yuri Gagarin State Technical University of Saratov; 2 Kotelnikov Institute of Radio- Engineering and Electronics, RAS, SB; 3 School of Electrical Engineering Aalto University; Russia

12:15-12:45 Code: ThR8-38, Invited

Kauranen Martti

Enhancing the nonlinear response of metamaterials

M. Kauranen¹, R. Czaplicki¹, J. Mäkitalo¹, H. Husu¹, M. Zdanowicz¹, R. Siikanen¹, K. Koskinen¹, J. Lehtolahti², J. Laukkanen², and M. Kuittinen²; 1 Tampere University of Technology, 2 University of Eastern Finland; Finland

12:45-13:15 Code: ThR8-39, Invited

Chipouline A.

Interaction of plasmonic nanostructures and quantum system: recent results

A. Chipouline; FSU Jena; Germany

13:15-13:30 Code: ThR8-40

Fedorov Sergey

Modes of Collective Lasing of a Chain of Spasers

S.V. Fedorov^{1,2}, A.V. Chipouline³, N.N. Rosanov^{1,2,4}; 1 University ITMO, 2 Vavilov State Optical Institute, Russia; 3 Friedrich Schiller University, Germany; 4 Ioffe Physical Technical Institute, Russia

13:30-13:45 Code: ThR8-41

Danilov Vladimir

Nonlinear optical effects in the near-IR range of semiconductor quantum structures in solutions

V.V. Danilov¹, A.I. Khrebtov¹, A.S. Panfutova¹, A.D. Bouraulev¹, V.Dhaka², H.Lipsanen²; 1 Vavilov State Optical Institute, 2 St. Petersburg State Transport University, 3 St. Petersburg Academic University, Russia; 4 Aalto University, Finland.

Thursday, July 3

Memorial session: Professor A.P. Sukhorukov and nonlinear optics**Poster presentations****Tuesday, July 1**

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p01

Henry Leanne J.

Investigation of Spectral Broadening Associated with a Raman Resonator Cavity

Leanne J. Henry, Jacob Grosek, Mike Klopfer, and Ravi Jain; Air Force Research Laboratory and the University of New Mexico, USA

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p02

Swiderski Jacek

High Average Power Mid-Infrared Supercontinuum Generation in a Fluorozirconate Fiber

Jacek Swiderski, Maria Michalska, and Lukasz Galecki ; Institute of Optoelectronics, Military University of Technology; Poland

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p03

Gerasimenko Alexandr

Investigation of laser limiters based on disperse and composite nanomaterials

A.Yu. Gerasimenko, I.I. Bobrinetskiy, E.A. Gerasimenko, L.P. Ichkitidze, M.S. Savelyev, V.M. Podgaetsky, S.A. Dolgushin ; National Research University of Electronic Technology (MIET); Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p04

Barantsev Konstantin

Spatial oscillations of index of refraction in the atomic medium with Doppler broadening

K.A. Barantsev, A.N. Litvinov; St. Petersburg State Polytechnical University, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p05

Kasyanov Ivan

Influence of thermal deformation processes on temperature parameters of nonlinear optical frequency conversion in LBO crystal

Yu. D. Arapov 1, V. A. Dyakov 2, S. G. Grechin 3, I. V. Kasyanov 1; 1 Russian Federal Nuclear Center - Zababakhin All-Russia Research Institute of Technical Physics, 2 Lomonosov Moscow State University, 3 Bauman Moscow State Technical University, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p06

Dorokhova Marta

Constructive interference of fundamental solitons in dispersion oscillating optical fiber

Marta Dorokhova, Leonid Melnikov, Andrey Konyukhov; The Yuri Gagarin State Technical University of Saratov; Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p07

Bisyarin Mikhail

Vortex Mode Soliton Propagation in Graded-Index Optical Fiber with Longitudinal Inhomogeneity

M.A.Bisyarin, I.M.Oreshnikov; St.Petersburg State University, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p08

Gagarskiy Sergey

Two-Photon Recording of Stable Luminescent Centers in Chromone-Doped Polymer Films

A. Ayt 1, V.A. Barachevsky 1, O.I. Kobeleva 1, T.M. Valova 1, S.V. Gagarskiy 2, V.V. Kiyko 2, A.N. Sergeev 2, A.V. Veniaminov 2, V.V. Zakharov 2, M. Krayushkin 3, Hristo Iglev 4; 1 Photochemistry Center RAS, 2 National Research University ITMO, 3 N.D. Zelinsky Institute of Organic Chemistry, Russia; 4 Technical University of Munich, Germany

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p09

Huang Ding-Wei

Impact of Kerr Effect on the Performance of Optical Invisibility Cloak Designed by Transformation Optics

Po-Han Fu, Hsiu-Chih Yeh, Wei-Chi Hsu and Ding-Wei Huang; National Taiwan University

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p10

Arapov Yu. D.

THERMO-OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF LBO CRYSTAL FOR ANGULAR NON- CRITICAL PHASE MATCHING FOR SECOND HARMONIC GENERATION ALONG X AXIS

Yu. D. Arapov 1, S. G. Grechin 2, I. V. Kasyanov 1; 1 Russian Federal Nuclear Center - Zababakhin All-Russia Research Institute of Technical Physics, 2 Bauman Moscow State Technical University, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p11

Sumarokov Alexander

NONLINEAR POLARIZATION OF TWO-LEVEL ATOMIC MEDIUM IN THE WEAK POLICHROMATIC FIELD

Alexander Sumarokov, Andrey Antipov, Alexey Kalinichev, Sergey Pulkin, Svetlana Uvarova; St. Petersburg State University, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p12

Yusupov Marsel

Effect of Finite Relaxation Rates and Round-trip Times on Regimes of Few-cycle Pulses in a Laser with Coherent Passive Mode-locking
M.R. Yusupov 1, N.V. Vysotina 1, N.N. Rosanov 1,2,3; 1 Vavilov State Optical Institute, 2 National Research University ITMO, 3 Ioffe Physical Technical Institute, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p13

Nesterov Leonid

Quantum Fluctuations of Dark Dissipative Solitons in Wide-Aperture Nonlinear Interferometers

L.A.Nesterov 1,2. N.A.Veretenov 1,2. N.N.Rosanov 1,2,3; 1 Vavilov State Optical Institute, Institute for Laser Physics, 2 National Research University ITMO, 3 Ioffe Physical Technical Institute, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p14

Vodchits Alexander

Stimulated Raman scattering of picosecond laser pulses at 532 nm in light and heavy water

A.I. Vodchits 1, V.A. Orlovich 1, V.S. Gorelik 2, Y.P. Voinov 2; 1 B.I. Stepanov Institute of Physics NAS Belarus, Belarus; 2 Lebedev Physical Institute RAS, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p15

Lis Denis

Molybdate crystals as host for downconversion materials

D.A. Lis 1, K.A. Subbotin 1, E.V. Zharikov 2, A.V.Khomyakov 2, 1 General Physics Institute RAS, 2 D.I. Mendeleev University of Chemical Technology; Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p16

Ladour Khadidja

Multi-resonant optical parametric oscillator based on 2D-PPLT nonlinear photonic crystals

Mohamed Lazoul 1, Khadidja Ladour 1, Lotfy Mokhtar Simohamed 1, Azzedine Boudrioua 2, Lung-Han Peng 3; 1 École Militaire Polytechnique Bordj El Bahri, Algeria; 2 Université de Paris, France; 3 National Taiwan University, Taiwan

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p17

Shukshin Vladislav

Raman Spectra and Structure Transformation of LBO Crystals During Heating and Melting

Yu.Voronko, A.Sobol', V.Shukshin; General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p18

Shandarov Vladimir

Diffraction properties of optically modulated laser-written 1D waveguide array in lithium niobate

A. Kanshu 1, V. Kruglov 1, A. Perin 1, D. Petnev 1, V. Shandarov 1, F. Chen 2; 1 State University of Control Systems and Radioelectronics, Russia; 2 Shandong University, China

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p19

Magnitskiy Sergey

Source of single correlated photons at 1.06- μ m wavelength

S.Magnitskiy 1, V.Firsov 1, N.Nagorskiy 1; I.Protsenko 2, M.Saygin 2; 1 Lomonosov Moscow State University, 2 Lebedev Physical Institute RAS, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p20

Arkhipov Rostislav

Theoretical Analysis of Coherent Passive and Self Mode-Locking in Lasers

R.M. Arkhipov1, M.V. Arkhipov2; 1 Weierstrass Institute for Applied Analysis and Stochastics, Leibniz Institute in Forschungsverbund Berlin e. V., Germany; 2 St. Petersburg State University, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p21

Korobko Dmitry

Generation of pulse trains with high-repetition-rate in anomalous dispersion decreasing fibers

Dmitry A. Korobko1, Oleg G. Okhotnikov 1,2, Alex A. Sysolyatin3, Igor O. Zolotovskii1; 1 Ulyanovsk State University, Russia; 2 Tampere University of Technology, Finland; 3 General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p22

Makarov Anton

Nonlinear optical properties of semiconductor thin films and multilayer structures containing such films

A. D. Makarov, A. A. Ryzhov, A. N. Baranov; Vavilov State Optical Institute, National Research University ITMO, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p23

Chirkin Anatoly

Multipartite entangled quantum states in coupled optical parametric interactions: density matrix and entropy characterization

A.S. Chirkin, M.Yu. Saygin and T.V. Tlyachev; Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: TuR8-p24

Perin Anton

Influence of the light propagation direction on the diffraction structures self-induced within the nonlinear Fabry-Perot interferometer
 A. S. Perin, V. M. Shandarov, V. G. Kruglov, V. F. Batrshin ; Tomsk State University of Control Systems and Radioelectronics; Russia

Session: R9. Microwave photonics (MWP)

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Thursday, July 3

09:00-09:30 Code: ThR9-01, Invited

Lavrinenko Andrei

Linear and nonlinear THz spectroscopy of materials and metamaterials
 Andrei V. Lavrinenko; Technical University of Denmark

09:30-10:00 Code: ThR9-02, Invited

Lai Ngoc Diep

Polymer-based photonic structures and applications in nonlinear optics

Mai Trang Do, Thi Thanh Ngan Nguyen, Qinggele Li, Isabelle Ledoux-Rak, Ngoc Diep Lai; École Normale Supérieure de Cachan, France

10:00-10:30 Code: ThR9-03, Invited

Timofeeva Tatiana

Engineering of Acentric Materials for NLO and THz Applications

Tatiana V. Timofeeva 1, Marina S. Fonari 1,2, Sergiu Draguta 1, Igor Denisyuk 3, Marina Fokina 3; 1 New Mexico Highlands University, USA; 2

Institute of Applied Physics Academy of Sciences of Moldova, Moldova; 3 National Research University ITMO, Russia;

10:30-10:45 Code: ThR9-04

Denisyuk Igor

Molecular nanocrystals for electro-optic application

Julia Burunkova, Igor Denisyuk, Marina Fokina; National Research University ITMO, Russia

10:45-11:00 Code: ThR9-05

Balia Vera

Microstrip optical waveguides made by RIE process

V. Balia, I. Denisiuk, V. Bulgakova, S. Pozdnyakova, D. Zhuk; National Research University ITMO, Russia

Thursday, July 3

11:30-11:45 Code: ThR9-06

Bulgakova Vera

Self-organization processes in nanocomposite materials at holographic recording for photonic crystal fabrication

V.Bulgakova, N. Vorzobova, I. Denisyuk; National Research University ITMO, Russia

11:45-12:00 Code: ThR9-07

Laszewski Henryk

Gold nanocomposites preparation and applications

Henryk Laszewski; Wroclaw University of Technology, Poland

12:00-12:15 Code: ThR9-08

Pavlovetc Ilia

Comparison study of non-centrosymmetric materials from aminopyridines

Ilia Pavlovetc 1, Igor Denisyuk 1, Marina Fokina 1, Tatiana V. Timofeeva 2, Marina Fonari 2, Sergiu Draguta 2; 1 National Research University

ITMO, Russia; 2 New Mexico Highlands University, USA

12:15-12:30 Code: ThR9-09

Petrov Alexey

Gain optimization of a fiber-optic link with an external electrooptical modulator and erbium doped fiber amplifier

A.Petrov 1, I. Ilichev 1, P.Arguzov 1, V. Lebedev 1, A.Shamray 1, E.Velichko 2; 1 Ioffe Physical Technical Institute RAS, 2 St. Petersburg State Polytechnical University, Russia

12:30-12:45 Code: ThR9-10

Pozdnyakova Svetlana

Optical nanocomposite materials for applications in Photonics

Svetlana Pozdnyakova, Igor Denisiyk, Julia Burunkova; National Research University ITMO, Russia

12:45-13:00 Code: ThR9-11

Skryl Anton

Photonic-electronic terahertz frequency comb spectroscopy
A.S. Skryl, D.G. Pavelyev, and M.I. Bakunov; University of Nizhny Novgorod, Russia

13:00-13:15 Code: ThR9-12

Sychugin Sergey
Terahertz Cherenkov radiation from a focused laser beam in an electro-optic medium
S.A. Sychugin, M.I. Bakunov; University of Nizhny Novgorod, Russia

Poster presentations

Thursday, July 3

15:00-19:00 Code: ThR9-p01

Kochkurov Leonid
Numerical model for investigation of dynamics of short-cavity two-color fiber laser for THz generation
L.A. Kochkurov, L.A. Melnikov, Yu.A. Mazhirina; Saratov State Technical University; Russia

15:00-19:00 Code: ThR9-p02

Salzenstein Patrice
Optical resonators based on carbon nanotubes for photonics applications
Patrice Salzenstein 1, Taron Makaryan 2; 1 CNRS FEMTO-ST, France, 2 Faculty of Radiophysics Yerevan State University, Armenia, Visiting Scientist at the department of Engineering - University of Cambridge, UK

15:00-19:00 Code: ThR9-p03

Salzenstein Patrice
Application of modern method of calculating uncertainty to microwaves and opto- electronics
E. Pavlyuchenko 1,2, P. Salzenstein 1; 1 CNRS FEMTO-ST, France; 2 Donetsk University, Ukraine

Session: SY1. 7th International Symposium on High-Power Fiber Lasers and Their Applications

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Tuesday, July 1

09:00-09:40 Code: TuSyl-01, Invited

Gapontsev Valentin
Progress of fiber lasers
V. Gapontsev; IPG Photonics, USA

09:40-10:20 Code: TuSyl-02, Invited

Dianov E
Bismuth-doped optical fibers - a new promising active medium for the near IR Spectral region
E Dianov; Fiber Optics Research Center RAS; Russia

10:20-11:00 Code: TuSyl-03, Invited

Unt A
Parallel Combining of Nanosecond High-power Pulse Fiber Lasers
A. Unt; IPG Laser GmbH, Germany

Tuesday, July 1

11:30-11:50 Code: TuSyl-04

Doronkin A
High power supercontinuum fiber source
A.V. Doronkin; NTO IRE-Polyus, Russia

11:50-12:10 Code: TuSyl-05

Larin Sergey
Model of bulk solid state optical amplifier with fiber combined single-mode signal and pump
S.V. Larin; NTO IRE-Polyus, Russia; NTO IRE-Polyus

12:10-12:30 Code: TuSyl-06

Myasnikov Daniil
Erbium FCPA system for ophthalmology and micromachining applications
D.V. Myasnikov; NTO IRE-Polus, Russia;

12:30-12:50 Code: TuSyl-07

Tyrtyshnyy V

Mode Instability in Yb 3+-doped LMA Fiber Amplifiers of Continuous and Pulsed Signal
V.A. Tyrtyshnyy; NTO IRE-Polus, Russia

12:50-13:10 Code: TuSyl-08

Baranov A

Numerical stability computation of ultrashort pulse generation in erbium fiber laser passively mode locked through nonlinear polarization rotation
A.I. Baranov; NTO IRE-Polyus, Russia

13:10-13:30 Code: TuSyl-09

Ulianov I

Ytterbium Mode-locked fiber laser with single-wall nanotubes as saturable absorber
I. Ulianov; NTO IRE-Polyus, Russia

Tuesday, July 1

15:00-15:20 Code: TuSyl-10

Protasenya D

Spectrum shift of ultrashort pulses generated in erbium passively mode-locked fiber laser
D.V. Protasenya; NTO IRE-Polyus, Russia

15:20-15:40 Code: TuSyl-11

Ovchinnikov A

Title to be announced - Laser Diodes for Pumping
A. Ovtchinnikov; IPG Photonics Corporation, USA

15:40-16:00 Code: TuSyl-12

Didierjean Julien

Single crystal fibers for laser amplification
Julien Didierjean; Fibercryst SAS, Décines-Charpieu, France

16:00-16:20 Code: TuSyl-13

Sandoval-Romero G. E.

Comparison of a Broadband Fiber Optic Source
G.E. Sandoval-Romero, E.F. Pinzon-Escobar; Centro de Ciencias Aplicadas y Desarrollo Tecnológico-UNAM, Mexico

16:20-16:40 Code: TuSyl-14

Vershinin O

Pulse control and pulse jitter stabilization in Cr:ZnSe-passively Q-switched Ho:YAG lasers
O.I. Vershinin; NTO IRE-Polus, Russia

16:40-17:00 Code: TuSyl-15

Larin Sergey

Comparison of novel all-fiber-format and hybrid thulium pulse fiber lasers
S.V. Larin; NTO IRE-Polus, Russia

Tuesday, July 1

17:30-17:50 Code: TuSyl-16

Obronov I

Investigation of the features of supercontinuum generation in single-mode passive fibers
I. Obronov; NTO IRE-Polyus, Russia

17:50-18:10 Code: TuSyl-17

Vinnichenko A

Urine stone fragmentation by short-pulse thulium fiber laser
A. Vinnichenko; NTO IRE-Polyus, Russia

18:30-18:50 Code: TuSyl-19

Vasilyev Sergey

Kerr-lens mode-locked mid-IR fs oscillators based on Cr-doped polycrystalline ZnS and ZnSe
S. Vasilyev 1, M. Mirov 1, V. Gapontsev 2, 1 IPG Photonics, Mid-IR Lasers; 2 IPG Photonics, USA

18:50-19:10 Code: TuSyl-20

Surin A

14 W SHG in MgO: sPPLT at 589 nm from high power CW linearly polarized RFL

A.A. Surin; NTO IRE-Polus, Russia

Wednesday, July 2

09:00-09:40 Code: WeSyl-21, Invited

Fomin V
100 kW CW Fiber Laser for Industrial Applications
V. Fomin; IPG Laser GmbH, Germany;

09:40-10:20 Code: WeSyl-22, Invited

Leontiev L
Title to be announced - Powders for laser technologies
L Leontiev; , Russia

10:20-11:00 Code: WeSyl-23, Invited

Smurov I
Title to be announced - Additive technologies
I Smurov;;

Wednesday, July 2

11:30-11:50 Code: WeSyl-24, Invited

Nosyrev Nikolay A.
High power fiber laser for hulls production in shipbuilding
Nikolay A. Nosyrev; JSC "Shipbuilding and Shiprepair Technology Center", Russia

11:50-12:10 Code: WeSyl-25

Drechsel Jan
High-speed laser welding of different steel grades with a 3 kW single-mode cw fiber laser
J. Drechsel, U. Loeschner, S. Schwind, M. Wagner, J. Schille ; Laser Institute at the University of Applied Sciences Mittweida; Germany

12:10-12:30 Code: WeSyl-26

Dury Noémie
Expansion of pulsed laser process limits through pulsed fiber lasers
N. Dury, C. Ruettimann, R. Holtz; ROFIN-LASAG AG; ROFIN-LASAG AG; Switzerland

12:30-12:50 Code: WeSyl-27

Gumenyuk Regina
All-fiber, high-power, picosecond Yb double clad tapered fiber amplifier
R. Gumenyuk 1, V. Filippov 1, Yu. Chamorovskii 2, A. Vorotinskii 1, K. Golant 2, O.G. Okhotnikov 1; 1 Tampere University of Technology, Finland; 2 Institute of Radio and Electronics RAS, Russia

12:50-13:10 Code: WeSyl-28

Lacroix Fabrice
Behavior of composite materials submitted to a 1.07 μm laser irradiation in the range of 100 to 2 kW/cm²
Olivier Muller ; ISL; France

13:10-13:30 Code: WeSyl-29

Lai Wenn Jing
Absorption studies of ring core double clad fiber
Wenn Jing Lai; Nanyang Technological University, Singapore

Wednesday, July 2

15:00-15:20 Code: WeSyl-30

Ustimchik Vasily
Multilayer W-type Optical Fibers for High-power Fiber Lasers.
V.E. Ustimchik^{1,2}, A.E. Ulanov^{1,2}, S.A. Nikitov^{1,2}, Yu.K. Chamorovskii¹, V.N. Filippov³; 1 Institute of Radio-engineering and Electronics RAS
2 Moscow Institute of Physics and Technology, Russia, 3 Tampere University of Technology, Finland

15:20-15:40 Code: WeSyl-31

Xiao Rongshi
High power fiber laser welding of thin sheet Al-Li alloy 2060-T8
Xinyi Zhang, Rongshi Xiao; Beijing University of Technology, China; P.R. China

15:40-16:00 Code: WeSyl-32

Zhang Yongqiang

Reflection Characteristic and Cutting Speed Calculation During Laser Cutting With High Power Fiber Laser in Air, Oxygen and Nitrogen Atmosphere

Y. Q. Zhang, J. He, Y. H. Tao; Institute of Fluid Physics, China Academy of Engineering Physics, China; P.R. China

16:00-16:20 Code: WeSyl-33

Shilov Igor

Mathematical model of penetration of the laser beam into the molten pool

I.V. Shilov, M.A. Tsibina; Kovrov State Technological Academy, Russia

16:20-16:40 Code: WeSyl-34

Yu Hailong

Nanosecond square pulses with triangular spectral profile generated from an all-normal-dispersion passively mode-locked Yb-doped fiber laser
Hailong Yu, Xiaolin Wang, Pu Zhou, Xiaojun Xu, and Jinbao Chen; College of Optoelectric Science and Engineering, National University of Defense Technology; P.R. China

16:40-17:00 Code: WeSyl-35

Ignatov A

Characteristics of laser welding imperfections, aspects of their appearance and removal as applied to high-power fiber lasers

N.V. Grezev, A.G. Ignatov; NTO IRE-Polyus, ITERA, Russia

Wednesday, July 2

17:30-17:50 Code: WeSyl-36

Dallarosa Joe

Title to be announced - Laser Devices for High-Precision Processing

Joe Dallarosa; IPG Photonics Corporation, USA;

17:50-18:10 Code: WeSyl-37

Holtz Ronald

Laser micro applications with pulsed fiber lasers

R. Holtz, D. Naman; Class 4 Laser Professionals AG, Switzerland;

18:10-18:30 Code: WeSyl-38

Petrovskiy V

Laser welding of aluminium alloys

V. Petrovskiy; National Research Nuclear Univ. "MEPhI", Russia

Thursday, July 3

09:00-09:40 Code: ThSyl-39, Invited

Turitsyn G

Title do be announced - Laser Welding

G.A. Turitsin; ILIST, Russia

09:40-10:20 Code: ThSyl-40, Invited

Babin Sergey

New schemes of Raman fiber lasers

S. Babin; Inst. of Automation and Electrometry SB RAS, Russia

10:20-11:00 Code: ThSyl-41, Invited

Mirov Sergey

Recent progress in 1.9 - 6 μm mid-IR lasers based on Cr and Fe doped II-VI chalcogenides

S. Vasilyev 1, M. Mirov 1, V. Gapontsev 2, V. Fedorov 3, D. Martyshkin 3, 1 IPG Photonics, Mid-IR Lasers; 2 IPG Photonics, 3 Univ. of Alabama at Birmingham, USA

Thursday, July 3

11:30-11:50 Code: ThSyl-42

Borisenko T

Investigation of high power SHG in MgO:PPLN crystal pumped by 1178 nm radiation from Raman fiber laser

T.E. Borisenko; NTO IRE-Polyus, Russia

11:50-12:10 Code: ThSyl-43

Byalkovskiy O

High power pulsed single-mode laser generation 630 nm by sum frequency mixing of Yb and Er lasers radiation in LBO crystal
O.A. Byalkovskiy; NTO IRE-Polyus, Russia

12:10-12:30 Code: ThSyl-44

Nikitin D

Sum frequency generation of UV laser radiation at 266 nm in LBO Crystal
D.G. Nikitin; NTO IRE-Polus, Russia

12:30-12:50 Code: ThSyl-45

Vershinin O

Anisotropy of UV-induced degradation of LBO crystal
O.I. Vershinin; NTO IRE-Polyus, Russia

12:50-13:10 Code: ThSyl-46

Semionov S

Recent advances in microstructured optical fibers
S.L. Semionov; Fiber Optics Research Center RAS, Russia

13:10-13:30 Code: ThSyl-48

Kostina M

Structure and characteristics of thin sheet laser welded joints of nitrogen content austenitic and martensitic steels
M.V. Kostina 1, S.O. Muradjan 1, E.V. Blinov 1, Yu. Petrov 1, S.D. Voronchuk 2, V.I. Krivorotov 2, L.V. Shamova 2; 1 IMET RAS, 2 NTO IRE-Polus, Russia

Thursday, July 3

15:00-15:20 Code: ThSyl-49

Voronchuk S

Performance assessment of full strength and tension of laser welds of nitrogen content, austenitic and martensitic steels
S.D. Voronchuk; NTO IRE-Polyus, Russia; NTO IRE-Polyus

15:20-15:40 Code: ThSyl-50

Dostovalov Alexandr

Long-period and fiber Bragg gratings fabricated by high-energy femtosecond pulses
A.V. Dostovalov; Institute of Automation and Electrometry SB RAS, Russia

15:40-16:00 Code: ThSyl-51

Puyu P

Visualization of UV-induced photorefractive damage in LBO crystals
P. Puyu; NTO IRE-Polyus, Russia

16:00-16:20 Code: ThSyl-52

Tsankov

Title to be announced - Fiber lasers in UV spectral region
Tsankov; NTO IRE-Polyus, Russia

Session: SY2. 3rd International Symposium on Lasers in Medicine

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Advanced Laser Systems for Medical Laser Applications - I

Thursday, July 3

09:10-09:35 Code: ThSY2-01, Invited

Osiko Vyacheslav

New Laser and RF Technologies for Medical Applications
Yu.K. Danileiko, V.V. Ezhov, V.V. Osiko, A.M. Shulutko; General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

09:35-10:00 Code: ThSY2-02, Invited

Sroka Ronald

1940nm Tm: fiber laser assisted treatment of hyperplastic nasal turbinates
Ronald Sroka, M.Havel, C. Betz, A. Leunig; LIFE-Centre at Hospital of University Munich, Germany

10:00-10:25 Code: ThSY2-03, Invited

Bagratashvili Victor

Laser-stimulated Cavitation and Tissue Regeneration
V. Bagratashvili; Institute of Laser and Information Technologies RAS, Russia

10:25-10:50 Code: ThSY2-04, Invited

Altshuler G.B.

Fractional laser treatment: a new method of tissue regeneration

G.B. Altshuler 1, A.V. Belikov 2; 1 Dental Photonics, Inc., USA; 2 National Research University ITMO, Russia; Dental Photonics, Inc.

10:50-11:15 Code: ThSY2-05, Invited

Minaev Vladimir

Medical Devices with Fiber Lasers and their Applications

V.P.Minaev; NTO "IRE-Polus"; Russia

Advanced Laser Systems for Medical Laser Applications - II

Thursday, July 3

11:30-11:55 Code: ThSY2-06, Invited

Panchenko Vladislav

Smart laser medical systems for cardiosurgery and oncology

V.Ya. Panchenko 1, I.I. Berishvili 2, V.V. Vasiltsov 1, V.A. Ul'yanov 1; 1 Institute of Laser and Information Technologies RAS, 2 Bakulev Center of Cardiovascular Surgery, Russia

11:55-12:20 Code: ThSY2-07, Invited

Boutoussov Dmitri

Potential of Synergetic Effect in Medical Laser Applications

Dmitri Boutoussov; Biolase, Inc., USA

12:20-12:45 Code: ThSY2-08, Invited

Lappa Alexander

0.97 and 1.56 μm lasers in treatment of degenerative-dystrophic bone diseases in children

I.A.Abushkin 1, V.A.Privalov 1, A.V.Lappa 2, N.V.Noskov 1, E.A.Neizvestnykh 1, A.N.Kotlyarov 1, Yu.G.Shekunova 1; 1 South Ural State Medical University, 2 Chelyabinsk State University, Russia.

12:45-13:05 Code: ThSY2-09

Larin Sergey

Power Tm-doped Fiber Lasers for Medical Applications

Sergey Larin 1, Andrey Mashkin 2, Fedor Shcherbina 2; 1 NTO IRE-Polus, Russia; 2 IPG Laser GmbH, Germany

13:05-13:25 Code: ThSY2-10

Kholin Vladimir

Experience of application of diode surgical laser "Lika-khirurg M" with a wavelength 445 nm in the field of aesthetic medicine

Tarasov N.1, Tarasova L.1, Goroshko S.1, Holin V.2, Pantyo V.3; 1 Center of laser and esthetic medicine, 2 Enterprise "Photonica Plus", 3 GVUZ "Uzhgorod national university", Ukraine

Optical Biomedical Diagnostics - I

Thursday, July 3

14:30-14:55 Code: ThSY2-11, Invited

Sroka Ronald

Investigations on fluorescence guided stereotactic biopsy

R. Sroka 1, G. Hennig 1, A. Johansson 1, A. Rühm 1, H. Stepp 1, W. Goebel 2, M. Goetz 3, J. Herms 4; 1 LIFE-Centre at Hospital of University Munich, 2 Karl Storz GmbH & Co KG, 3 MRC Systems GmbH, 4 Institute of Neuropathology, Germany

14:55-15:20 Code: ThSY2-12, Invited

Lasser Theo

Coherent Imaging from Tissue to Cell

Theo Lasser; EPFL, Switzerland

15:20-15:45 Code: ThSY2-13, Invited

Larin Kirill

Tissue Diagnostics using Optical Coherence Elastography

K.V. Larin, University of Houston, USA

15:45-16:10 Code: ThSY2-14, Invited

Maslennikova Anna

Diagnostics of radiation induced tissue damage and remodeling by laser scanning microscopy with second harmonic generation

A. Maslennikova 1, M. Kochueva 1, S. Kuznetsov 1, E. Kiseleva 1, V. Kamensky 2, N. Ignatjeva 3, O. Zakharkina 3, K. Babak 4, V. Dudenkova 4; 1

Nizhny Novgorod State Medical Academy, 2 Institute of Applied Physics RAS, 3 Institute of Laser Information Technologies RAS, 4 N.I.Lobachevsky State University, Russia

16:10-16:30 Code: ThSY2-15, Invited

Blondel Walter

Spatially resolved multimodal in vivo spectroscopy data fusion for discriminating precancerous states

Walter Blondel 1,2, Faiza Abdat 1,2, Marine Amouroux 1,2, Yann Guermeur 3,4; 1 Université de Lorraine, CRAN, 2 CNRS CRAN, 3 Université de Lorraine, LORIA, 4 CNRS, LORIA, France

16:30-16:50 Code: ThSY2-16

Leahy Martin J.

Imaging the human microcirculation

Martin J. Leahy; National University of Ireland, Ireland

Optical Biomedical Diagnostics - II

Thursday, July 3

17:10-17:35 Code: ThSY2-17, Invited

Nikitin Petr

Biosensors based on Spectral Correlation Interferometry for Biomedical Research and Diagnostics

P.I. Nikitin, A.V. Orlov, M.P. Nikitin, T.I. Ksenevich, B.G. Gorshkov; General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

17:35-18:00 Code: ThSY2-18, Invited

Stepanov Eugene

Application of lasers for high-sensitive breath content analysis and noninvasive biomedical diagnostics

E.V.Stepanov; General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

18:00-18:20 Code: ThSY2-19

Lilge Lothar

Optical tissue spectroscopy for stratification of entry into advanced cancer screening programs; Here demonstrated for the Breast

Lothar Lilge, Jane Walter, Jennifer Street, Brenda Ornelas-Lilge; University Health Network Princess Margaret Cancer Centre, Canada

18:20-18:40 Code: ThSY2-20

Bulgakova Natalia

Laser-induced fluorescence in dentistry

I.A. Schugailov 1, M. D. Egorjan 1, A.N. Makximenko 1, N. N. Bulgakova 2; 1 Russian Medical Academy of Postgraduate Education, 2 General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

18:40-19:00 Code: ThSY2-21

Ho Siu Chun

Fiber Bragg Grating Based Vascular Localization Device

Siu Chun Michael Ho 1, Mehdi Razavi 2, Gangbing Song 1; 1 Univ. of Houston, 2 Texas Heart Inst., USA

Laser Tissue Interaction - I

Friday, July 4

09:00-09:25 Code: FrSY2-22, Invited

Goryaynov Sergey

Multimodal intraoperative navigation in neurosurgery

A.A. Potapov 1, S.A. Goryaynov 1, T.A. Saveleva 2, V.B. Loschenov 2; 1 N.N. Burdenko Institute of Neurosurgery of RAMS, 2 General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

09:25-09:50 Code: FrSY2-23, Invited

Lilge Lothar

Augmentation of ALA mediated PDT of GBM by use of hypothermia and Tyrosine Kinase inhibitors.

Carl Fisher, Carolyn Nui, Lothar Lilge; Princess Margaret Cancer Institute/University of Toronto, Canada

09:50-10:15 Code: FrSY2-24, Invited

Mazayshvili Constantin

Mechanism of endovenous laser ablation

C.V. Masayshvili 1, Yu.M. Stoyko 1, V.B. Loshenov 2, G.A. Meerovich 2, A.V. Tsyplyashchuk 1; 1 Pirogov Medical and Surgery center, 2 General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

10:15-10:40 Code: FrSY2-25, Invited

Gamaleia Nikolai

Promising alliance of photodynamic therapy and nanotechnologies

N.F. Gamaleia; R.E. Kavetsky Institute for Experimental Pathology, Oncology and Radiobiology NAS Ukraine, Ukraine

10:40-11:00 Code: FrSY2-26

Lilge Lothar

Novel Ru and Os based NIR activatable Photosensitizers, therapeutic index under normoxic and hypoxic conditions and initial in vivo results
Ge Shi, Jamie Fong, Susan Monro, Kamola Kasimova, Robie Hennigar, Ryan DeCoste, Colin Spencera, Julie Colpitts, Lance Chamberlain, Arkady Mandel, Lothar Lilge and Sherri A. McFarland; Acadia University, Theralase Technologies, Inc., Princess Margaret Cancer Institute/University of Toronto, Canada

Laser Tissue Interaction - II

Friday, July 4

11:30-11:55 Code: FrSY2-27, Invited

Loshchenov Maxim

Combined videofluorescent and spectroscopic approaches in optical diagnostics of nervous system malignancies
M.V. Loshchenov, A.A.Potapov, P.V.Zelenkov, S.A. Goryaynov, D.A. Gol'bin, A.V.Borodkin, K.G.Linkov; General Physics Institute RAS, N.N. Burdenko Institute of Neurosurgery of RAMS, Russia

11:55-12:20 Code: FrSY2-28, Invited

Zharova Tatiana

Videofluorescent navigation during arthroscopic PDT of major joints
S.V.Ivannikov 1, M.V.Loshchenov 2, A.V. Borodkin 2, T.A.Zharova 1, V.I.Makarov 2, A.M.Tonenkov 1; 1 I.M. Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University, 2 General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

12:20-12:45 Code: FrSY2-29

Kuznetsova Julia

OCT Imaging-characterization and medical applications
J. O. Kuznetsova 1,2, G. Scheib 2, R. Sroka 2, M. Trottmann 2, R. Leeb 2, C. Homann 2; 1 General Physics Institute RAS, Russia; 2 Laser-Forschungslabor Klinikum der Universität Munich, Germany

12:45-13:05 Code: FrSY2-30

Kholodtsova Maria

Particle swarm optimisation algorithm for Monte Carlo-based inverse problem solving
M.N. Kholodtsova 1,2,3, V.B. Loschenov 1, C. Daul 2,3, W. Blondel 2,3; 1 General Physics Institute RAS, Russia; 2 CRAN, UMR 7039, 3 CNRS, CRAN, UMR 7039, France

13:05-13:25 Code: FrSY2-31

Klimenko V.V.

Different photodynamic effect between continuous wave and pulsed laser irradiation modes in k562 cells in vitro
V.V. Klimenko 1, A.A. Bogdanov 1, N.A. Knyazev 1, A.A. Rusanov 2, M.V. Dubina 1; 1 St. Petersburg Academic University, 2 First Pavlov State Medical University, Russia; St. Petersburg Academic University

Poster presentations

Thursday, July 3

19:00-20:30 Code: ThSY2-p01

Churkin Dmitry

Ophthalmic system based on excimer KrCl laser (223 nm)
A.M. Razhev 1,2, V.V. Chernykh 3, S.V. Kostenev 3, D.S. Churkin 1,2, E.S. Kargapol'tsev 1; 1 Institute of Laser Physics SB RAS, 2 Novosibirsk State University, 3 The S.N. Fyodorov FSI IRTC "Eye Microsurgery"; Institute of Laser Physics SB RAS; Russia

19:00-20:30 Code: ThSY2-p02

Kuznetsova Julia

Laser Spectroscopy Study Of The Distribution Of Photosensitizers In Biological Models
J.O. Kuznetsova 2, A.S. Saidov 1, N.A. Kalyagina 2, D.M. Yagudaev 1,3 ; 1 FGBI "Teaching and Research Medical Center", 2 General Physics Institute RAS, 3 State Clinical Hospital 151, Moscow; Russia

19:00-20:30 Code: ThSY2-p03

Guseva Irina

Detection of hypoxia and inflammatory processes in tissues by fluorescence spectroscopy in vivo
E. Petritskaya, L. Abaeva, D. Lapitan, D. Kulikov, O.Smirnova, I. Guseva, D. Rogatkin; Moscow Regional Research & Clinical Institute "MONIKI" named after M.F. Vladimirovskiy; Russia

19:00-20:30 Code: ThSY2-p04

Lapitan Denis

Modeling of the input signal in Laser Doppler Flowmetry
Lapitan D.G., Rogatkin D.A.; Moscow Regional Research and Clinical Institute "MONIKI" named after M.F. Vladimirovskiy; Russia

19:00-20:30 Code: ThSY2-p05

Tiganova I.G.

Photodynamic therapy of bacterial biofilms using new cationic photosensitiser.

I.G. Tiganova 1, G.A. Meerovich 2, T.V. Stepanova 1, J.S. Koloskova 3, S.S. Brusov 3, M.A. Grin 3, A.F. Mironov 3, J.M. Romanova 1; 1 Gamaleya Research Institute for Epidemiology and Microbiology, 2 A.M.Prokhorov General Physics Institute, 3 M.V.Lomonosov Moscow State University of Fine Chemical Technology, Russia

Session: SY2-C. Course on Biomedical Optics in Clinical Applications

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Friday, July 4

09:00-09:45 Code: FrCl-01

Soussen Charles

Confocal fluorescence microscopy and force-volume imaging in atomic force microscopy: A signal processing perspective
Charles Soussen; University of Lorraine, CRAN (Centre de Recherche en Automatique de Nancy), France

09:45-10:30 Code: FrCl-02

Loschenov M.V.

Videofluorescent devices for intraoperative diagnostics
M.V. Loschenov; General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

10:30-11:15 Code: FrCl-03

Sroka Ronald

Endovascular laser treatment and optical coherence tomography

Ronald Sroka 1, K. Siegrist 1, M. Heide 1, T. Pongratz 1, C.G. Schmedt 2; 1 LIFE-Centre at Hospital of University Munich, 2 Diakonie-Klinikum Schwäbisch Hall GmbH, Germany

Friday, July 4

11:30-12:15 Code: FrCl-04

Savelieva Tatiana

Processing of diffuse reflectance signal for spectroscopy and spectral imaging
T.A. Savelieva; General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

12:15-13:00 Code: FrCl-05

Lilge Lothar

What is the potential benefit for PDT treatment planning and real time dosimetry on the attainable outcome?
L. Lilge; Princess Margaret Cancer Institute/University of Toronto, Canada

Session: YS. 7th International Conference on Laser Optics for Young Scientists and Engineers

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Tuesday, July 1

09:00-09:45 Code: TuYS-01, Invited

Zhang Xi-cheng

The Institute of Optics, OSA and Optics Letters.
Zhang Xi-cheng; University of Rochester, USA

09:45-10:15 Code: TuYS-02, Invited

Gorodetsky Andrei

Recent Advances in Terahertz Technology
A. Gorodetsky; Aston University, UK

10:15-10:30 Code: TuYS-03

Grachev Yaroslav

Universal terahertz time-domain spectrometer for transmission and reflection measurements in life science: health and food testing
Y.V. Grachev, S.V. Smirnov, A.N. Tcypkin, V.G. Bepalov; National Research University ITMO, Russia

10:30-10:45 Code: TuYS-04

Khodzitsky Mikhail

Electromagnetic metamaterial devices for terahertz frequency range
M. Khodzitsky; National Research University ITMO, Russia

10:45-11:00 Code: TuYS-05

Kulya Maksim

Experimental set-up for holographic multiwavelength phase imaging

N.V.Petrov 1, M.S.Kulya 1, A.N.Tcypkin 1, A.A.Gorodetsky 2, V.G. Bespalov 1; National Research University ITMO, Russia; 2 Aston University, UK

Tuesday, July 1

11:30-12:00 Code: TuYS-06, Invited

Pyayt Anna

Optimization of On-Chip Blood Coagulation Sensor

S. Cheemalapati, H. Tuazon, A. Pyayt; University of South Florida, USA

12:00-12:15 Code: TuYS-07

Duka Maria

Stimulation of neurite growth under influence of broadband terahertz pulsed radiation

MV Duka (Tsurkan)1, MI Sulatskiy1, VA Penniyaynen2, AV Kipenko2, EV Lopatina2, BV Krilov2, OA Smolyanskaya1; 1 National Research University

ITMO, 2 Pavlov Institute of Physiology, Russia

12:15-12:30 Code: TuYS-08

Smolyanskaya Olga

Terahertz spectral characteristics and optical properties of normal and pathological skin, cornea and their components

O.A. Smolyanskaya; National Research University ITMO, Russia

12:30-12:45 Code: TuYS-09

Martynov V.O.

Numerical Simulation of Contrast Inversion Process when Focusing Laser Beam in the Absorbing Medium

E.L. Bubis, V.O. Martynov; Institute of Applied Physics RAS, Russia

12:45-13:00 Code: TuYS-10

Anchikov Dmitriy

Ordered vortex lattice in wide-aperture lasers

D.A. Anchikov, A.A. Krents, N.E. Molevich, A.V. Pahomov; Samara State Aerospace University, Samara branch of Physical Institute RAS, Russia

13:00-13:15 Code: TuYS-11

Kinyaevskiy IgorMID-IR BROADBAND FREQUENCY CONVERSION OF LASER RADIATION IN ZnGeP₂, GaSe AND AgGaSe₂ CRYSTALS

A.A. Ionin 1, I.O. Kinyaevskiy 1, Yu.M. Klimachev 1, A.A. Kotkov 1, A.Yu. Kozlov 1, Yu.M. Andreev 2; 1 Lebedev Physical Institute RAS, 2

Institute of Monitoring of Climatic and Ecological Systems SB RAS, Russia;

13:15-13:30 Code: TuYS-12

Malyshev Mikhail

Prospect of optically pumped oxygen-iodine lasers

Mikhail Malyshev 1, Marsel Zagidullin 2 ; 1 Samara State Aerospace University, 2 Lebedev Physical Institute RAS; Russia

Wednesday, July 2

09:00-09:30 Code: WeYS-13, Invited

Makarov Nikolay

Ultrafast spectroscopy helps optimize third-generation quantum dot solar cells

N.S. Makarov1, Q. Lin2, H. McDaniel1, K. A. Velizhanin3, C. M. Cirloganul, L.A. Padilha1, W.-K. Kohl, N. Fuke4, I. Robell, J.M. Pietrygal,

V.I. Klimov1; 1 Center for Advanced Solar Photophysics, Los Alamos National Labs, 2 Department of Chemical Engineering, New Mexico State Univ.,

3 Theoretical Division, Los Alamos National Labs, USA; 4 Materials & Energy Technology Laboratories, Sharp Corporation, Japan

09:30-09:45 Code: WeYS-14

Makeev Aleksey

Investigation of Mirrors Anisotropy Effect on the Gyro Non Plane Ring Laser

V.Azarova, A.Makeev; R&D Institute "Polyus", Russia

09:45-10:00 Code: WeYS-15

Pavlov NikolayOptical properties of heterostructures with deep quantum wells AlSb/InAs_{0.86}Sb_{0.14}/AlSb

N.V. Pavlov, G.G. Zegrya; Ioffe Physical Technical Institute RAS, Russia

10:00-10:15 Code: WeYS-16

Xiao Hu

Strict single-mode high power 1018 nm fiber laser operating in multimode Yb-doped fiber

Hu Xiao, Jinyong Leng, Xiaolin Wang, Yanxing Ma, Pu Zhou; National University of Defense Technology, China; P.R. China

10:15-10:30 Code: TuYS-17

Isaeva Anna

Spatially resolved speckle correlometry in application to media structure characterization

A.A. Isaeva 1, E.A. Isaeva 2; 1 National Research University ITMO, 2 Saratov State Technical University, Russia

10:30-10:45 Code: WeYS-18

Zasedatelev Anton

Linear optical properties of quantum dots - gold particle hybrid nanostructures.

A.V. Zasedatelev 1, V.S. Vasileva 1, A.N. Generalova 2, A.B. Karpo 3, V.I. Krasovskii 1,3, I.N. Feofanov 4, A.A. Chisryakov 1 and V.A.

Oleynikov2; 1 National Research Nuclear University 'MEPhI', 2 Shemyakin-Ovchinnikov Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry RAS, 3 A.M. Prokhorov General Physics Institute RAS, 4 Lebedev Physical Institute RAS, Russia

10:45-11:00 Code: WeYS-19

Sedov Evgeny

Storage of Optical Information in Nano-size Cavity Arrays Under The Qubit-Light Interaction

E.S. Sedov, A.P. Alodjants, S.M. Arakelian; Vladimir State University named after A.G. and N.G. Stoletovs, Vladimir, Russia

Wednesday, July 2

11:30-11:45 Code: WeYS-20

Kolesnichenko Pavel

Optical Properties of Quantum-Dimensional Probes of Scanning Probe Microscopes

P.V.Kolesnichenko, S.A.Pulkin, St. Petersburg State University, Russia

11:45-12:00 Code: WeYS-21

Gleim Artur

Subcarrier wave quantum cryptography system with loss-loss polarization compensation unit

A.Gleim, V.Egorov, Yu.Nazarov, S. Kynev, A.Rupasov, S. Chivilikhin; National Research University ITMO, Russia

12:00-12:15 Code: WeYS-22

Kapoyko Yury

One-and-half-cycle pulse duration evolution in nonlinear media

Yu.A. Kapoyko; National Research University ITMO, Russia

12:15-12:30 Code: WeYS-23

Buyanovskaya Elizaveta

Theoretical study of nonlinear Fabry-Perot interferometer for few-cycle pulses

Elizaveta Buyanovskaya, Egor Kryshkovets; National Research University ITMO, Russia

12:30-12:45 Code: WeYS-24

Konev Leonid

Effect of Raman nonlinearity on forward and backward waves of intense few-cycle laser field in optical fibre

L.S. Konev, Yu.A. Shpolyanskiy; National Research University ITMO, Russia

12:45-13:00 Code: WeYS-25

Khorkov Kirill

Surface modification of refractory metals by femtosecond laser radiation

D.A. Kochuev, K.S. Khorkov, D.V. Abramov, Affiliation1, Vladimir State University, Russia

Poster presentations**Tuesday, July 1**

15:00-19:30 Code: TuYS-p01

Parchanski Vaclav

Er-doped oxychalcogenide glasses - materials for nonlinear infrared optics

V. Parchanski 1, L. Støižík 1, B. Frumarova 2, J. Oswald 2; 1 University of Pardubice, 2 Czech Academy of Sciences Prague; Czech Republic

15:00-19:30 Code: TuYS-p02

Krents Anton

Spiral waves in large aperture laser model

A.A. Krents 1,2; D.A. Anchikov 1,2; N.E. Molevich 1,2; A.V. Pahomov 1,2; 1 Samara State Aerospace University, Russia; 2 Samara branch of Physical Institute of RAS, Russia.

15:00-19:30 Code: TuYS-p04

Kondratyuk Nikolay

Four-wave optical parametric oscillator with two different BBO crystals

D. Goman, N. Kondratyuk, A. Protasenya; Solar Laser Systems, Belarus

15:00-19:30 Code: TuYS-p05

Lednev Vasily

Laser Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy of Single Wall Carbon Nanotubes and Gold Nanoparticles in Aqua Solutions

S.M. Pershin 1, A.N. Fedorov 1, A.A. Serkov 1, R.N. Yulmetov 1, S.I. Kudryashov 2, S.V. Makarov, A.A. Ionin 2; 1 General Physics Institute RAS; 2 Lebedev Physical Institute RAS, Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: TuYS-p06

Kuptsov Gleb

The Seed Signal for the Parametric Amplification Channel of Multiterawatt Femtosecond Laser System

A.V. Laptev 1, E.V. Pestryakov 1, G.V. Kuptsov 1,2, V.A. Petrov 1,2, V.V. Petrov 1,2; 1 Institute of Laser Physics SB RAS; 2 Novosibirsk State Technical University, Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: TuYS-p07

Azarova Valentina

Spectroscopic ellipsometry metrology of precision optical surfaces and thin films

V. Azarova, A.Kulagin, V. Fokin; R&DI "Polyus", Russia;

15:00-19:30 Code: TuYS-p08

Puzyrev Danila

Collimation and focusing of initially single-cycle paraxial optical beams

D.N.Puzyrev, A.A. Drozdov; National Research University ITMO, Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: TuYS-p09

Rogov Pavel

Particularities of Femtosecond Radiation Interaction with Biological Objects

P Rogov, V Bespalov; National Research University ITMO, Russia

Session: SM1. Seminar on Optoelectronics

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Tuesday, July 1

09:00-09:30 Code: TuSml-01, Invited

Fan Kuang-Chao

Measurement of microstructures to super resolution by focus probe

Kuang-Chao Fan, Liang-Chia Chen; National Taiwan Univ. , Taiwan

09:30-10:00 Code: TuSml-02, Invited

Kosolobov Sergey

Atomic scale silicon surface processing for nanostructuring and precise surface measurements

Sergey S. Kosolobov^{1,2}, Sergey V. Sitnikov^{1,2}, Alexander V. Latyshev^{1,2}, Eugeny V. Sysoev³, Yuri V. Chugui^{2,3,4}; 1 Rzhanov Inst. of Semiconductor Physics SB RAS; 2 Novosibirsk State Univ., 3 Technological Design Inst. of Scientific Instrum.; 4 Rzhanov Inst. of Semiconductor Physics of SB RAS, Novosibirsk State Univ., Russia

10:00-10:30 Code: TuSml-04, Invited

Korolkov Victor

Metrological and technological limitations for correction of wavefront distortion in laser crystals by 3D photolithographic surface shaping

V.P. Korolkov¹, R.K. Nasyrov¹, A.G. Poleshchuk¹, Yu. D. Arapov², A.F. Ivanov²; 1Inst. of Automation and Electometry SB RAS, Russia; 2Russian Federal Nuclear Centre All-Russian Inst. of Technical Physics, Russia

10:30-10:45 Code: TuSml-05

Angelsky O.V.

The use of optical correlation algorithm to solve phase problem of complex optical fields

O.V. Angelsky, M.P.Gorsky, C.Yu. Zenkova, P.A.Ryabiy; Chernivtsy National Univ., Ukraine

10:45-11:00 Code: TuSml-03

Chen Liang-Chia

Development of in-situ one-shot confocal surface profilometry using double-slit chromatic differential confocal microscopy (CDCM)

Liang-Chia Chen*, Jiun-Da Lin, Kuang-Chao Fan, National Taiwan University, Taiwan

Tuesday, July 1

11:30-11:45 Code: TuSml-06

Ivanov Oleg

Fiber-optic bend sensor based on a section of double-cladding fiber

O.V. Ivanov 1, I.V. Zlodeev 2; 1 Ulyanovsk Branch of Kotel'nikov Institute of Radio Engineering and Electronics RAS, 2 Ulyanovsk State University; Russia

11:45-12:00 Code: TuSml-07

Obraztsov V.S.

Testing of optical homogeneity of materials in IR spectral region

V.I. Venzel, A.V. Gorelov, V.S. Obraztsov, M.I. Sinel'nikov, E.S. Egorova, N.Ya. Kuznetsova, Ye.S. Lavrent'ev; Scientific Research Inst. for Optoelectronic Instrument Engineering, PLC, Russia

12:00-12:15 Code: TuSml-08

Sapozhnikova Kseniia

Is it possible to enhance music influence by colour accompaniment?

K. Sapozhnikova, R. Taymanov, Mendeleev Inst. for Metrology, Russia

12:15-12:30 Code: TuSml-09

Konyakhin Igor

Optic-electronic autocollimator for control deformations of the axle at the millimeter wave range radiotelescope

I. Konyakhin, A. Usik, F. Molev, R. Li; National Research University ITMO, Russia

12:30-12:45 Code: TuSml-10

Sysoev Evgeny V.

Overcoming the diffractive limit of lateral resolution of 3D nanorelief measurements

E.V. Sysoev1, I.A. Vykhrstyuk1, R.V. Kulikov1, Yu.V. Chugui1,2,3; 1Technological Design Inst. of Scientific Instrument Engineering, SB RAS, 2 Novosibirsk State Univ., 3 Novosibirsk State Technical Univ., Russia

12:45-13:00 Code: TuSml-11

Zenkova Claudia Yu.

The use of nanoparticles of the Rayleigh light scattering mechanism in the metrology of optical currents and fields

C.Yu. Zenkova, I.V. Soltys; Chernivtsi National University, Ukraine

13:00-13:15 Code: TuSml-12

Chugui Yu.V.

Optical measuring technologies and systems for scientific and industrial applications

Yu.V. Chugui1,2,3, A.G. Verkhoglyad1, P.S. Zavyalov1; 1 Technological Design Inst. of Scientific Instrument Engineering SB RAS, 2 Novosibirsk State Univ., 3 Novosibirsk State Technical Univ., Russia

13:15-13:30 Code: TuSml-13

Arkhelyuk Aleksandr

Spectral-selective Mueller-matrix images of laser autofluorescence of biological tissues

Yu.A. Ushenko, A.D. Arkhelyuk; Chernivtsi National University, Ukraine

Tuesday, July 1

15:00-15:15 Code: TuSml-14

Korolkov V.P.

Monitoring of reactive ion etching of computer-generated holograms by specular spectroscopic scatterometry

A.S. Konchenko1, V.P. Korolkov1,2, A.I. Malyshev1, A.R. Sametov1; 1 Inst. of Automation and Electometry SB RAS, 2 Novosibirsk State Univ., Russia

15:15-15:30 Code: TuSml-15

Azarova Valentina

About metrology and applications of precision laser surfaces & mirrors

V.V. Azarova; RDI "Polyus" ; Russia

15:30-15:45 Code: TuSml-16

Chertov Aleksandr N.

Apparatus for analyzing the spectral characteristics of reflection, albedo and color parameters of flat objects

E.V. Gorbunova, V.V. Korotaev, E.A. Lastovskaya, A.N. Chertov, National Research University ITMO, Russia

15:45-16:00 Code: TuSml-17

Dubolazov Alexander

Polarization Selection of Birefringence Polycrystalline Networks of Blood Plasma Layers

Yu.O. Ushenko, A.V. Dubolazov, A.O. Karachevtsev, V.O. Savich, V.P. Prysiashniuk; Chernivtsi National University, Ukraine

16:00-16:15 Code: TuSml-18

Gorbachev Alexey

System for blade's output edge measuring in low pressure cylinder of closed turbine

D. Apehtin, A.Gorbachev, National Research University ITMO, Russia

16:15-16:30 Code: TuSm1-19

Dubolazov Alexander

Evolution of Mueller Matrix Images of the Myometrium for the Optical Anisotropy Oncological Changes

Yu.O. Ushenko, A.V. Dubolazov, A.O. Karachevtsev, O.I. Olar, V.O. Savich; Chernivtsi National University, Ukraine;

16:30-16:45 Code: TuSm1-20

Trushkina Anna V.

Polarization properties of crystal and polymer phase plates at their collimation turns in space

V.V. Korotaev, V.A. Ryzhova, A.V. Trushkina, National Research University ITMO, Russia

16:45-17:00 Code: TuSm1-21

Dubolazov Alexander

Fourier-Stokes Polarimetry of Fields Scattered by Birefringence Biological Tissues

Yu.O. Ushenko, A.V. Dubolazov, A.O. Karachevtsev, O.Yu. Novakovska, V.O. Savich; Chernivtsi National University, Ukraine;

Tuesday, July 1

17:30-17:45 Code: TuSm1-22

Shlychkov Vladimir

Laser thickness gauges calibration

V. Shlychkov, Ural Federal State Univ., Russia; Ural Federal State University, Russia

17:45-18:00 Code: TuSm1-23

Nehrych Andrey

Polymer-dispersed liquid crystals filter of spatial-frequency

Peter P. Maksimyak, Andrey L. Nehrych; Chernivtsi National University, Ukraine

18:00-18:15 Code: TuSm1-24

Yermolenko Sergey B.

Polarimetry and spectropolarimetry techniques in biotissue's cancer changes diagnostics

S.B.Yermolenko¹, O.P.Peresunko², N.V. Zelinska²; ¹ Chernivtsi National University; ² Bukovinian State Medical University, Ukraine

18:15-18:30 Code: TuSm1-25

Gavrylyak Mykhaylo

The investigation of thrombus formation process in blood plasma by correlation- optical technique

M.S. Gavrylyak P.P. Maksimyak; Chernivtsi National University, Ukraine

18:30-18:45 Code: TuSm1-26

Yermolenko Sergey B.

Spectropolarimetry diagnostic of blood plazma in patients with breast cancer

O.P. Peresunko¹, T.V. Kruk¹, S.B. Yermolenko*², P.V. Ivashko²; ¹ Bukovinian State Medical University, ² Chernivtsi National University, Ukraine

18:45-19:00 Code: TuSm1-27

Ivashko Pavlo V.

Modelling of light scattering in biotissue

P.V. Ivashko, Chernivtsi National University, Ukraine; Chernivtsi National University, Ukraine

19:00-19:15 Code: TuSm1-28

Gorsky Mykhailo

Laser light scattering by the cement during hydration process

M.P. Gorsky, P.P. Maksimyak; Chernivtsi National University, Ukraine

Poster presentations

There are no poster presentations in this session.

Session: SM2. Seminar on Terahertz Photonics

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Monday, June 30

15:00-15:30 Code: MoSm2-01, Invited

Kulipanov Gennady

NovoFEL - tunable high power source of terahertz radiation: new results and perspectives

G. Kulipanov ¹, E. Chesnokov ², B. Knyazev ^{1,5}, V. Kubarev ^{1,5}, S. Peltek ³, A. Petrov ², V. Popik ¹, O. Shevchenko ¹, S. Veber ⁴, N.

Vinokurov ^{1,5}; ¹ Budker Institute of Nuclear Physics RAS, ² Institute of Chemical Kinetics and Combustion SB RAS, ³ Institute of Cytology and

Genetics SB RAS, 4 International Tomography Center SB RAS, 5 Novosibirsk State University, Russia

15:30-16:00 Code: MoSm2-02, Invited

Bratman V.l.

Novel Versions of Terahertz Electron Devices

V.L. Bratman, A.E. Fedotov, Yu.K. Kalynov; Institute of Applied Physics RAS, Russia

16:00-16:30 Code: MoSm2-03, Invited

Kubarev Vitaly

Ultrafast Real-Time THz Time-domain Spectroscopy on NovoFEL

V.V. Kubarev^{1,2}, E.N. Chesnokov³, and P.V. Koshlyakov³ 1 Budker Institute of Nuclear Physics, Russia; 2 Novosibirsk State University, Russia; 3 Institute of Chemical Kinetics and Combustion, Russia

16:30-17:00 Code: MoSm2-04, Invited

Glyavin Mikhail

The development of THz gyrotrons and their applications for plasma science and diagnostics of various media

Mikhail Yu. Glyavin¹, Grigory G. Denisov¹, Vladimir E. Zapevalov¹, Evgheniy M. Tai²; 1 Institute of Applied Physics RAS, 2 GYCOM Ltd, Russia

17:00-17:30 Code: MoSm2-05, Invited

Vaks Vladimir

THz Quantum Cascade Lasers For High Resolution Spectroscopy

Vladimir Vaks; Institute for physics of microstructures RAS, Russia

17:30-17:45 Code: MoSm2-06

Nazarov Maxim

High refractive polymer materials based on the silicon nano- and micro- particles.

M.M. Nazarov¹, E.V. Khaydukov¹, V.I. Sokolov¹, A.G. Savelyev¹, A.P. Shkurinov², V.Ya. Panchenko¹; 1 Institute on Laser and Information Technologies RAS, 2 Moscow State University, Russia

17:45-18:00 Code: MoSm2-07

Gerasimov Vasily

Terahertz surface plasmon polaritons: new results at the Novosibirsk free-electron laser

V.V. Gerasimov¹, V.O. Gorovoy²; 1 Budker Institute of Nuclear Physics SB RAS, 2 Novosibirsk State University, Russia

Tuesday, July 1

09:00-09:30 Code: TuSm2-08, Invited

Son Joo-Hiuk

Challenges in Medical Applications using Terahertz Waves

Joo-Hiuk Son; University of Seoul, Korea

09:30-10:00 Code: TuSm2-09, Invited

Knyazev Boris

Prospects for Terahertz Optics and Spectroscopy with Tunable Monochromatic Radiation Sources

B.A. Knyazev^{1,2}, G.N. Kulipanov¹, N.A. Vinokurov^{1,2}; 1 Budker Institute of Nuclear Physics SB RAS, Russia; 2 Novosibirsk State University, Russia

10:00-10:15 Code: TuSm2-10

Shkurinov Alexander

Terahertz Image Processing for the Skin Cancer Diagnostic

Alexey Balakin¹, Alexander Kolesnikov², Peter Solyankin¹, Andrey Angeluts¹, Maxim Nazarov¹, Maxim Evdokimov¹, Melissa Spencer⁴, Anatoliy

Nikitin², Alexander Shkurinov¹, Valery Tuchin^{2,3}, Anna Yaroslavsky⁴; 1 Lomonosov Moscow State University, 2 Saratov State University, Russia; 3 University of Oulu, Finland; 4 University of Massachusetts Lowell, USA

10:15-10:30 Code: TuSm2-11

Zaytsev Kirill

Signal Processing and Algorithms for Inverse Problem in THz Time-Domain Spectroscopy

Kirill I. Zaytsev¹, Valeiy E. Karasik¹, Nikita V. Chernomyrdin¹, Arseniy A. Gavdush¹, Irina N. Fokina¹, Pavel A. Nosov¹, Stanislav O. Yurchenko¹, Konstantin G. Kudrin², Igor V. Reshetov²; 1 Bauman Moscow State Technical University, 2 Gertsen Moscow Research Institute of Oncology, Russia

10:30-10:45 Code: TuSm2-12

Fokina Irina

Simulation of THz scattering in partly-ordered medium

I.N. Fokina, K.I. Zaytsev, S.O. Yurchenko, V.E. Karasik, V.S. Gorelik; Russia

10:45-11:00 Code: TuSm2-13

Zavyalova Marina

Near-Field Terahertz Scanning Optical Microscope with Frustrated Total Internal Reflection Module

A. G. Verkhogliadl, V. V. Gerasimov^{2,3}, M. A. Zavyalov^{1,3}, B. A. Knyazev^{2,3}, S. N. Makarov^{1,3}, M. F. Stupak^{1,3}, D. G. Rodionov^{2,3,4}, Yu. Yu. Choporova^{2,3}; 1 - Technological Design Institute of Scientific Instrument Engineering SB RAS; 2 - Budker Instrument Engineering SB RAS; 2 - Budker Institute of Nuclear Physics SB RAS; 3 - Novosibirsk State University; 4 - Novosibirsk State Technical University Novosibirsk; Russia

Tuesday, July 1

11:30-12:00 Code: TuSm2-14, Invited

Simoens François

THz real-time imaging with specifically designed uncooled silicon bolometer 2D array camera
François Simoens; CEA Leti-MINATEC, France

12:00-12:30 Code: TuSm2-15, Invited

Khokhlov Dmitry

THz probing of local electron states in doped lead telluride-based semiconductors
D.R. Khokhlov^{1,2}, L.I. Ryabov¹, 1 Lomonosov Moscow State Univ., Russia, 2 Lebedev Physical Inst. RAS, Russia

12:30-13:00 Code: TuSm2-16, Invited

Gol'tsman Gregory

Overview of recent results for superconducting NbN terahertz and optical detectors and mixers
G.N. Gol'tsman; Moscow State Pedagogical University, Russia

13:00-13:30 Code: TuSm2-17, Invited

Koshelets Valery

Superconducting Integrated Terahertz Spectrometers

V.P. Koshelets¹, P.N. Dmitriev¹, L.V. Filippenko¹, N.V. Kinev¹, O.S. Kiselev¹, K.I. Rudakov¹, G. de Lange², V.L. Vaks³, J. Yuan⁴, H.B. Wang⁴; 1 Institute of Radio Engineering and Electronics RAS, Russia; 2 SRON Netherlands Institute for Space Research, The Netherlands; 3 Institute for Physics of Microstructure RAS, Russia; 4 National Institute for Materials Science, Japan

Tuesday, July 1

15:00-15:30 Code: TuSm2-18, Invited

Park Kyung Hyun

Semiconductor beating sources for tunable continuous-wave terahertz generation and its industrial application

Kyung Hyun Park¹, Namje Kim¹, Kiwon Moon¹, Eui Su Lee¹, Il-Min Lee¹, Hyunsung Ko¹, Jeong-Woo Park¹, and Sang-Pil Han¹, Min Youn Jeon², Han-Cheol Ryu³; 1 THz Photonics Creative Research Center, 2 ChungNam National University, 3 Samyook University; THz Photonics Creative Research Center; Korea

15:30-16:00 Code: TuSm2-19, Invited

Kitaeva Galiya

Measurement of the spectral brightness under nonlinear-optical terahertz wave detection

G. Kh. Kitaeva, P. V. Yakunin, V. V. Kornienko, A. N. Penin; Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia

16:00-16:30 Code: TuSm2-20, Invited

Coutaz Jean Louis

Terahertz vectorial antennas based on cubic electro-optic crystals

G. Gaborit, A. Biciunas and J.-L. Coutaz, IMEP-LAHC, Univ. of Savoie, France

16:30-17:00 Code: TuSm2-21, Invited

Bakunov Michael

Cherenkov-type terahertz emission spectroscopy of ultrafast optomagnetic effects

M.I. Bakunov¹, S.D. Gorelov¹, R.V. Mikhaylovskiy², S.B. Bodrov¹, E.A. Mashkovich¹, and M.V. Tsarev¹; 1 University of Nizhny Novgorod, Russia; 2 Radboud University Nijmegen, The Netherlands

Tuesday, July 1

17:30-18:00 Code: TuSm2-22, Invited

Tzortzakis Stelios

Nonlinear strong field THz effects

S. Tzortzakis^{1,2}; 1 Institute of Electronic Structure and Laser (IESL), 2 University of Crete, Greece

18:00-18:30 Code: TuSm2-23, Invited

Kosareva Olga

Coherent THz Radiation Emitted from Femtosecond Filaments in Gases

O.G. Kosareva¹, N.A. Panov¹, V.A. Andreeva¹, A.P. Shkurinov¹, V.A. Makarov¹, L. Berge², and S.L. Chin³; 1 Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia; 2 CEA, DAM, DIF, France; 3 Université Laval, Canada

18:30-18:45 Code: TuSm2-24

Fadeev Daniil

THz generation from rough metall surfaces irradiated by femtosecond laser pulses
 D.A. Fadeev, V.A. Mironov, I.V. Oladyshkin, E.V. Suvorov, R.A. Akmedzhanov, I.E. Ilyakov, B.V. Shishkin; Institute of Applied Physics RAS, Russia

18:45-19:00 Code: TuSm2-25

Andreeva Vera

Infrared and terahertz radiation generation under filamentation of two-color femtosecond laser pulse
 V.A. Andreeva, N.A. Panov, O.G. Kosareva; M.V. Lomonosov State University & International Laser Center, Russia

19:00-19:15 Code: TuSm2-26

Oladyshkin I.V.

Cherenkov radiation of the laser pulse envelope in the process of the semimetal reflection
 V. A. Mironov, I.V. Oladyshkin; Institute of Applied Physics RAS, Russia

19:15-19:30 Code: TuSm2-27

Mamrashev Alexander

Investigation of methods enhancing weak terahertz signals detection effectiveness
 A. A. Mamrashev, N. A. Nikolaev; Institute of Automation and Electrometry, Russia

Poster presentations

Wednesday, July 2

15:00-19:30 Code: WeSm2-p01

Ryu Han-Cheol

Simple Terahertz Continuous-wave Applications based on a Compact Dual Mode Laser
 H.-Ch. Ryu 1, K. H. Park 2; 1 Sahmyook University, 2 ETRI, Korea

15:00-19:30 Code: WeSm2-p02

Germanskiy Semyon

The study of correlation properties of optical-terahertz biphoton pairs generated by the spontaneous parametric down-conversion
 S.A. Germanskiy, G.Kh. Kitaeva, V.V. Kornienko, A.N. Penin; Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: WeSm2-p03

Ushakov Aleksandr

The study of THz wave generation dependence on mutual polarization of two-color pump fields
 Aleksandr Ushakov1, Pavel Chizhov2, Roman Volkov1, Vladimir Bukin2, Sergey Garnov2, Andrey Savel'ev1; 1 Lomonosov Moscow State University, 2 General Physics Institute RAS, Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: WeSm2-p04

Cherkasova Olga

Application of terahertz spectroscopy in biomedical research
 O. P. Cherkasova1, M.M.Nazarov2, A.A. Angeluz3, I. N. Smirnova4, A. P. Shkurinov3; 1 Institute of Laser Physics SB RAS, 2 Institute on Laser and Information Technologies RAS, 3 Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia; 4 Nagoya University, Japan

15:00-19:30 Code: WeSm2-p05

Chesnokov Evgeni

Non-Faraday Rotation of the Free Induction Decay in Terahertz Region.
 E.N. Chesnokov1, V.V. Kubarev1,2, P.V. Koshlyakov1; 1 Institute of Chemical Kinetics and Combustion, 2 Budker Institute of Nuclear Physics, 3 Novosibirsk State University, Russia

15:00-19:30 Code: WeSm2-p06

Choporova Yulia

Classic Holography in the Terahertz Range: Recording and Reconstruction Techniques
 Yu. Choporova, M. Mitkov; Budker Institute of Nuclear Physics SB RAS, Russia

Session: Post-deadline

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Wednesday, July 2

17:30-17:40 Code: WePD-01

Vartanyan Tigran

Use of Selective Reflection process to study "forbidden" atomic transitions of Cs D2 line
 A. Sargsyan 1, A. Amiryanyan 1, D. Sarkisyan 1, T.A. Vartanyan 2; 1 Institute for Physical Research NAS of Armenia, Armenia; 2 National Research University ITMO, Russia

17:40-17:50 Code: WePD-02

Vedin Ivan

High-Efficiency Thin-Disk Laser Based on Tm-doped KLu(WO₄)₂/KLu(WO₄)₂ Composite Crystal

S.M. Vatnik 1, I.A. Vedin 1, P.F. Kurbatov 1, A.A. Pavlyuk 2; 1 Institute of Laser Physics SB RAS, 2 Institute of Inorganic Chemistry SB RAS, Russia

17:50-18:00 Code: WePD-03

Kuzin Ruslan

Measurement of optical inhomogeneities of a cesium vapor laser by means of a Hartmann-Shack sensor

A.A. Babin, O.I. Beloshitskaya, V.A. Bogachev, S.G. Garanin, M.A. Gluhov, M.O. Koltygin, A.V. Kopalkin, R.S. Kuzin, S.M. Kulikov, A.N. Manachinsky, S.N. Nosov, F.A. Starikov, S.A. Suharev, V.V. Feoktistov; RFNC - VNIIEF, Russia

18:00-18:10 Code: WePD-04

Zavestovskaya Irina

Laser Metal Nanoparticles Fragmentation

I.N. Zavestovskaya; Lebedev Physical Institute RAS; National Research Nuclear University "MEPhI", Russia

18:10-18:20 Code: WePD-05

Kiselev Valery

The generation of singlet oxygen in aqueous suspensions of carbon nanoparticles

V.M. Kiselev 1, I.V. Bagrov 1, A.M. Starodubtsev 1, A.N. Burchinov 2, I.M. Kislyakov 3; 1 Vavilov State Optical Institute, Russia; 2 St. Petersburg State University, Russia; 3 University ITMO, Russia

18:20-18:30 Code: WePD-06

Barettin Daniele

Random alloy fluctuations effects on the spontaneous emission properties of a InGaN/GaN LED

M. Auf der Maur 1, D. Barettin 1, A. Pecchia 2, A. di Carlo 1; 1 Department of Electronic Engineering University of Rome "Tor Vergata", 2 CNR-ISMN, Italy

18:30-18:40 Code: WePD-07

Onushchenko A A.

PbS Doped Silicate Glasses for Radiation Control in Near IR Lasers: Optical and Structural Characterization

A A. Onushchenko 1, V. V. Golubkov 2, S. A. Kalmykov 3, D .I. Staselko 4; 1 NITIOM, 2 Institute of Silicate Chemistry, 3 Ioffe Physical-Technical Institute, 4 Rozhdestvensky Optical Society, Russia;